

Advanced PSyclone Training for HPC Experts

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1. Introduction

This is the training material for the usage of PSyclone, a code transformation and generator tool. PSyclone was originally developed for the UK Met Office's new LFRic numerical weather prediction system, but its features of modifying large codes based on scripts have found other use cases, for example NOAA's Tsunami model MOST (Method of Splitting Tsunamis) and Nemo (Nucleus for European Modelling of the Ocean) are both using it.

There are three different user groups that will be using PSyclone. Firstly, research who will be using any model that uses PSyclone for code transformation will see PSyclone being used during the build process, and in case of errors might need to be able to have a very high-level understanding to diagnose the reason for the error. Secondly, natural scientists who want to write code using the code generation capabilities will need to be aware of PSyclone's rules. Lastly, HPC experts who are writing recipes (or scripts) to optimise code need to have a much deeper understanding of PSyclone's internal data structure, behaviour and features.

This manual is the material to accompany a two-day training course for HPC experts, i.e. the last user group. It does start with one session "PSyclone for LFRic Users", which is a suitable introduction for the first user group. This part is actually part of the official LFRic training. But it is also a valuable introduction for HPC experts, and as such is included here.

The 2-day training course is a sequence of presentations, followed by a hands-on session to allow the trainees to try the concepts introduced in a simple test case. Some of the hands-on sessions are more open ended, and trainees are encouraged to go back to these examples and implement better solutions later.

This material contains a short introduction for each session, followed by the slides, and then the explanations and tasks for the hands-on session.

2. PSyclone for LFRic Users

This first session of the training material introduces the high-level concepts of PSyclone. It is actually part of the official LFRic training for users, but also a good introduction for advanced users. It explains the advantage of the separation of concerns that PSyclone supports, namely that the science code is independent of (potentially) hardware-specific optimisations. This separation makes the code more readable, and allows natural scientist to work on code development at the same time that HPC experts implement parallelisation and code optimisations. This will also result in making natural scientists more productive, since many previously manual and error-prone tasks are now automated.

This session does not go into any details about coding. It focuses on the point of view of user, to identify which files are the input for PSyclone, and which files are automatically created. This is important in helping with potential build failures, since e.g. a file created by PSyclone will not be stored in a versioning repository. So, enabling the users to know which files are the actual input files will allow them to look e.g. at the versioning history of a file.

The hands-on session allows user to run PSyclone on some simple code, and study the changes that PSyclone and its optimisations scripts can automatically apply to code. It also contains some examples with errors, so users can get experience with the error message, and how to identify the reason for errors.

2.1 PSyclone for LFRic Users - Slides

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PSyclone for LFRic Users

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V1.1

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Target Audience

PSyclone for users of LFRic

- Focus is on using PSyclone in LFRic
 - Not development/coding for LFRic (or PSyclone)
 - Not HPC experts
 - Though it is a general introduction into PSyclone for these groups as well
 - There will be more specific training for these user groups
- It explains why PSyclone was developed and what it does
 - High level concepts only
- Hands-on session will give you the opportunity to see exactly what PSyclone does
 - And what to look out for if it should fail

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What Will you Learn?

- At the end of this presentation, you will:
 - Understand what PSyclone is and why it is being developed
 - Understand what PSyclone does (or at least can do) to source files
 - Understand the PSyclone command line options
 - Identify which files are important in case of an error
 - Esp. which files should be in a repository, and which ones are automatically created

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Outline

- Why PSyclone?
- What does PSyclone do?
- What are the files involved and created?
- The PSyclone command line
- LFRic build system
- Hands on session
- Summary

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What Problem does PSyclone Solve (1) ?

Based on Most Tsunami Code (NOAA)

```

call HaloExchange(da, ...)
!$OMP PARALLEL DO default(none) private(j) shared(...)
do j=1,nx
  dw(1:ny)=da(j,1:ny)
  call swlat(uw,qw,vw,dw,ny)
enddo
!$OMP END PARALLEL
...
call swlon(...)
...
subroutine swlat(...)
  do i=1, ny
    d2=GA*t*((dw(i+1)-dw(i))/h(i)-(dw(i)-dw(i-1))/h(im))
    ul(i)=uw(i)+r1-t1*(3.*uw(i-1)+qw(i-1)+3.*uw(i+1)
  
```

MPI parallelisation

Optimisation

Shared memory parallelisation

Generically boring loop stuff ☹️

Interesting science
 😊

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Wouldn't it be Nice to Write

```

call swlat(uw,qw,vw,dw)
call swlon(...)
...
subroutine swlat(...)
  ...
  d2=GA*t*((dw(i+1)-dw(i))/h(i)-(dw(i)-dw(i-1))/h(i-1))
  ul(i)=uw(i)+r1-t1*(3.*uw(i-1)+qw(i-1)+3.*uw(i+1)
  
```

- PSyclone is getting close to this
 - As we will see it needs a bit of additional information

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What Problem does PSyclone Solve (2)

- Natural scientists / developers want to/should focus on science to be more productive
 - Not concerned about parallelisation, optimisations
 - Scientists can focus on science, instead of debugging parallelisation or code optimisations
 - This can better be done by computational scientists / HPC experts

- Ideally, optimisation and parallelisation should be independent of science code
 - Avoid rewriting existing code over and over
 - Avoid too much porting effort (which can introduce new errors)

- The code might need to be rewritten/optimised depending on target platform
 - Pre-processor directives (`#ifdefs`) with site-specific implementation are NOT a solution
 - They are mostly a means of code obfuscation
 - And they don't solve the issue of code duplication

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The Three Ps

- Productivity
 - Not concerned about parallelisation, optimisations
 - Scientists can focus on science, instead of debugging parallelisation or code optimisations
 - This can better be done by computational scientists / HPC experts

- Performance
 - Avoid rewriting existing code over and over
 - Avoid too much porting effort (which can introduce new errors)

- Portability
 - Pre-processor directives (`#ifdefs`) with site-specific implementation are NOT a solution
 - They are mostly a means of code obfuscation
 - And they don't solve the issue of code duplication

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Is PSyclone the Only Software Doing This?

- There are other projects with similar ideas:
- Kokkos
 - <https://github.com/kokkos/kokkos>
 - C++ based template library & performance-portability framework
- Loki (ECMWF)
 - Python transformation utility, no official release yet
- Claw (maybe abandoned?)
 - <https://claw-project.github.io/>
 - Mainly code transformation, but supports Fortran
- Dawn/GTClang
 - <https://github.com/MeteoSwiss-APN/dawn>
 - Optimizer and code generation library for DSL to create C++

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Separation of Concerns

- PSyclone provides an embedded domain-specific language
 - Allows science developers to focus on:
 - What algorithms do I want to implement?
 - In which order do I want to execute these algorithms?
 - How is the science for each operation implemented?
- PSyclone provides code generation
 - Automatically creates loops
- PSyclone provides transformations to optimise and parallelise code
 - All using scripts developed by computational scientists

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Scientist's View

- I want to do:


```
call compute_temperature(new_temp, old_temp)
call compute_radiation(...)
call compute_pressure(...)
```

 - Operating on whole fields – where *fields* are LFRic-specific objects provided by LFRic infrastructure
- And this is done as:


```
subroutine compute_temperature_kernel(new_temp, old_temp)
! For a single 'element'
new_tmp = f(old_tmp)
end subroutine compute_temperature_kernel
```

 - View of a single 'element', where an 'element' is a section of a standard Fortran array
- Now please glue all of this together
 - Add the loops over elements
 - Convert the LFRic-specific objects into arrays to be provided to the kernel

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What is an Element?

- One element in LFRic is one column
 - Picture left shows two columns
- Each kernel must loop over its column
- Different function spaces, e.g.:
 - W0: blue vertices
 - W1: edge (not shown)
 - W2: face (not shown)
 - W3: red dots for a cell

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Multiple Invokes and Kernel Calls in an Algorithm Layer

- An invoke might contain several kernel calls:


```
call invoke( setval_c( r_rho, 0.0_r_def ), &
             project_eos_rho_kernel_type( r_rho, exner, theta, &
             moist_dyn(gas_law), &
             chi, panel_id, kappa, &
             rd, p_zero, qr ), &
             dg_matrix_vector_kernel_type( rho, r_rho, m3_inv ) )
```
- And obviously you can have several invokes in one subroutine
- PSyclone will create
 - One module source file
 - One subroutine for each invoke statement in this module
 - Each subroutine contains loops around a call statement for each kernel called

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Kernel Files

- These files contain the actual science code
 - Compute one element, i.e. one column in LFRic. E.g.:


```
do k = 0, nlayers-1
  do df = 1, ndf_wx
    chi1_e(df) = chi1(map_wx(df) + k)
    chi2_e(df) = chi2(map_wx(df) + k)
    chi3_e(df) = chi3(map_wx(df) + k)
  end do
  ...
```
- They also contain meta-data, which tells PSyclone which parameters to expect, which kind of loop to create etc:


```
type(arg_type) :: meta_args(3) = (/
  arg_type(GH_FIELD, GH_REAL, GH_READWRITE, ANY_DISCONTINUOUS_SPACE_1),
  arg_type(GH_FIELD*3, GH_REAL, GH_READ, ANY_SPACE_9),
  arg_type(GH_FIELD, GH_REAL, GH_READ, ANY_DISCONTINUOUS_SPACE_3) /)
```

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Files Used and Created in LFRic

- `.x90/ .X90` indicates a file to be processed by PSyclone
 - LFRic naming convention
- For `my_alg_mod.x90` PSyclone will create:
 - A new replacement algorithm file:
→ `my_alg_mod.f90`
 - A newly created PSy-layer file:
→ `my_alg_mod_psy.f90`
- The `.x90` file is never compiled (in theory it could, but it would not produce anything useful)
 - The created `.f90` and `_psy.f90` files are compiled instead of the algorithm layer `.x90` file
 - The kernel layer is compiled as is.
- Only the `.x90` files (and kernel files) should be version controlled
 - The created algorithm and PSy-layer files are automatically created and should not be versioned

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LFRic Coding Style

- <https://code.metoffice.gov.uk/trac/lfric/wiki/LFRicTechnical/FortranCodingStandards>
- Coding style dictates assumptions made by PSyclone to find the kernel files:
 - A file `xxx_mod.F90/f90/X90/x90` must contain the module `xxx_mod`
 - A file `xxx_alg_mod.x90` is an algorithm layer file. It creates:
 - `xxx_alg_mod.f90` (algorithm layer)
 - `xxx_alg_mod_psy.f90` (PSy-layer)
 - A kernel module `xxx_kernel_mod` defines a type `xxx_kernel_type`
 - `xxx_kernel_type` provides a subroutine `xxx_code`, which is called by the PSy-layer
- In case of errors, this naming scheme will allow you to know where the sources come from
 - E.g. `my_func_code` not found → look for kernel file `my_func_kernel_mod.f90`
 - `my_func_kernel_type` not found → it should be in the kernel file `my_func_kernel_mod.f90`
 - `invoke_my_func` not found → this is in the PSy-layer, `my_func_mod_psy.f90`
 - Though it can also be a processing error of the algorithm file, not creating the proper PSy-layer file

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LFRic Builtins

- Some common linear algebra operations are provided by PSyclone as a builtins
 - There is no actual kernel that implements this function
 - Instead PSyclone will inline the code directly
- Full overview of builtins:
 - <https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/dynamo0p3.html#naming-scheme>
- Most kernels operate on an 'element' that is a column
 - Builtins operate on a single finite element (i.e. a single scalar)
 - Some kernels operate on a whole field (i.e. no loop in PSy-layer) – physics kernel

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PSyclone Command Line Options

```
psyclone -api dynamo0.3 -l all
-d working/gungho
-oalg working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod.f90
-opsy working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod_psy.f90
working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod.x90
```

- The API specifies what kind of loops PSyclone will create (and what field types to use etc)
 - Will be renamed to 'lfric' with the next release (and is already used in hands-on session)
- `-l all` restricts all output files to have lines of less than 132 characters
- `-d working/gungo` tells PSyclone where to look for kernel files
- `-oalg` specified the output filename of the algorithm layer
- `-opsy` the output filename of the PSy layer
- The standard parameter is the name of the algorithm file
- This will only create the source files, which then need to be compiled separately.

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Distributed Memory Parallelisation – aka MPI

- PSyclone can automatically create MPI code
- Computation of the domain decomposition and distribution of the data is still the task of the actual code
- PSyclone will take care of 'halo exchanges'
 - And if you don't know what this is, that's ok ☺
Just be aware that PSyclone does clever things for you here
- Command line option: `-dm:`

```
psyclone -dm -api dynamo0.3 -l all -d working/gungho  
-oalg working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod.f90  
-opsy working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod_psy.f90  
working/gungho/algorithm/set_rho_alg_mod.x90
```

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Applying Transformation Scripts

- PSyclone can apply scripts to transform the code before writing it out
 - Can be used to e.g. add shared-memory parallelism (OpenMP, OpenACC for GPUs), or other optimisations
- These scripts will be written by computational scientists or other specialists
- The LFRic build systems is responsible for finding the scripts.
 - File specific scripts are stored in `optimisations/SITE/PATH_OF_X90_FILE/file.py`
 - Generic scripts to be applied for any (other) file, are in `optimisations/SITE/global.py`

```
psyclone -dm -api dynamo0.3 -l all -d working/gungho  
-s optimisation/generic-x86/global.py  
-oalg working/gungho/field/r_solver_field_vector_mod.f90  
-opsy working/gungho/field/r_solver_field_vector_mod_psy.f90  
working/gungho/field/r_solver_field_vector_mod.x90
```

- If `-s` is missing (build with `VERBOSE=1`) when building LFRic, your site might not have required optimisation scripts
 - Though some LFRic apps do not require scripts at all.

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PSyclone Configuration

- PSyclone uses a configuration file to specify certain default values¹
 - Distributed memory (DM)
 - ... see <https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/configuration.html>
- LFRic requires a modified config file
 - It is now included in lfric core (.../lfric_core/etc/psyclone.cfg)
 - PSyclone 2.5 (release end of February 2024) fixed this

¹ Currently there is a default API, but that is going to be removed with the next release

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Integration of PSyclone in the LFRic Build System

Simplified ... and Pre-FAB

1. All builds are done in a 'working' directory
2. Copy all the source files into the working directory
 - Typically, source for the model and the infrastructure files from the LFRic root directory
 - All .F90 and .X90 files are being pre-processed
 - PSyclone does not support preprocessor directives
3. Automatically create some source files to read in namelist configuration files
4. Run PSyclone on all .x90 files
 - Optimisation scripts are picked up from .../optimisations/SITE/global.py or file-specific
5. Run the dependency analysis to determine order of compilation
6. Compile all .o files
7. Link everything together
 - (FAB works in similar phases, which are better separated – and will support the same script logic)

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Summary

- PSyclone defines three layers:
 - Algorithm layer: operate on whole fields
 - PSy-layer: contains the loop over elements and other parallelisation code
 - Kernel layer: apply operation on one element
- It supports separation of concerns:
 - This allows natural scientist to focus on their science
 - And HPC experts to focus on parallelisation and optimisation
- Porting to different hardware platforms can be done in scripts
 - Independent of the actual science code

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Hands-on Session

- Investigate PSyclone's behaviour for a very trivial kernel
- See what an optimisation and parallelisation script can do
 - MPI, OpenMP, hybrid
- See error messages
 - And how to fix some of them
- Skip example 7 (commented out already)
 - Will likely be moved into a different training modules
- There is a `README.md` in the directory, but you can also look at the nicer version at: https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone/tree/1623_add_training/tutorial/training/users/lfric

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Setup

Venv:

```
module load python3/3.12.1
git clone -b 1623_add_training https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone.git
cd PSyclone
python3 -m venv venv
source ./venv/bin/activate
python3 -m pip install .
cd tutorial/training/users/lfric/
```

To reactivate:

```
module load python3/3.12.1
cd ../PSyclone
source ./venv/bin/activate
cd tutorial/training/users/lfric
```

https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone/tree/1623_add_training/tutorial/training/users/lfric

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Thank you

Contact me on Joerg.Henrichs@bom.gov.au

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2.2 Simple PSyclone Application

Directory: PSyclone/tutorial/training/users/lfric

This directory contains a very trivial example code that is based on the LFRic infrastructure and PSyclone. It uses the simplified infrastructure files used in PSyclone testing, and as such can be compiled and run without the need to install LFRic.

There is no need to fully understand the program, but as a quick explanation: the program creates two fields on a 3x3 mesh with 5 layers. The field `field_0` is on the vertices of the finite element (W0 function space, blue in the diagram below, which only shows a 1x2x4 mesh, not the full 3x3x5), and is initialised with 1. The field `field_3` is on the W3 function space (red in the diagram) and represents the actual element, it is initialised with 0.

Then the kernel `summation_w0_to_w3_kernel` is called, which adds the 8 neighbouring vertices of an element up (resulting in 8 for all the finite elements). The summation for the top left element is indicated in the image with dashed lines:

Each of the following examples has its own subdirectories with the required files. In order to run the tests, change into the subdirectory specified in the heading. The required PSyclone command is specified in this document, but in all cases you can also just run `make` in order to run PSyclone with the required parameters. Most examples can also be compiled (`make compile`) and executed (`make run`). The only exception are the MPI examples (since the LFRic infrastructure files that are used in LFRic are a cut down version which do not include actual MPI support). The OpenMP kernels have been extended to print the thread-id, so you can actually see that different threads are being used.

2.2.1 Using PSyclone

Subdirectory: 1_using_psyclone

In this example we use PSyclone to process the algorithm file and create the new algorithm layer and PSY-layer file. To create the required PSY-layer, use the following command:

```
psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -nodm -l output
         -opsy main_alg_psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90
         main_alg.x90
```

The same command can be triggered by `make`. This will create two new output files, `main_alg.f90`, the rewritten algorithm layer `main_alg.x90`, and `main_alg_psy.f90`, the created PSY-layer.

Look at the two created files. You don't need to try to understand the details, since PSyclone is creating quite a bit of code. Identify how the main program, the algorithm layer, calls the PSY-layer, and how the PSY-layer calls the kernel in a loop. Focus on the first two invokes in `main_alg.x90`:

```

call invoke( name = 'Initialise fields',      &
             setval_c( field_3,      0.0_r_def ), &
             setval_c( field_0,      1.0_r_def ) &
             )
call invoke( name = 'summation', summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_
             type(field_3, field_0) )

```

How are these lines rewritten in the algorithm file `main_alg.f90`? Then check the PSy-layer file `main_alg_psy.f90` to find the two subroutines called from the algorithm file. Can you find the builtins in the PSy-layer file `main_alg_psy.f90`? And check the loop over all columns that will then call `summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_code` for each column.

You can even compile and execute the script: `make compile` will create a binary for you (including compilation of the required LFRic infrastructure, which can take some time). Executing the binary with `./example` will print:

```

Mesh has          5 layers.
20230905101141.609+1000:INFO : Min/max minmax of field_3 =
0.800000000E+01  0.800000000E+01

```

The minimum and maximum of `field1` are printed, and they are as expected 8.

Explanation

The file `main_alg.f90` contains two calls to a PSy layer:

```

CALL invoke_initialise_fields(field_3, field_0)
CALL invoke_summation(field_3, field_0)

```

In turn the `main_alg_psy.f90` files contains these two subroutines. The first one contains the implementation of the builtins, i.e. the code is inlined:

```

!
! Call our kernels
!
DO df=loop0_start,loop0_stop
  field_3_proxy%data(df) = 0.0_r_def
END DO
DO df=loop1_start,loop1_stop
  field_0_proxy%data(df) = 1.0_r_def
END DO

```

The second subroutine contains the call of the test kernel:

```

!
! Call our kernels
!
DO cell=loop0_start,loop0_stop
  !
  CALL summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_code(nlayers,      &
                                     field_3_proxy%data, field_0_proxy%data, &
                                     ndf_w3, undf_w3, map_w3(:,cell),      &
                                     ndf_w0, undf_w0, map_w0(:,cell))
END DO

```

Note that PSyclone will automatically provide additional required parameters to the kernel.

2.2.2 Supporting MPI

Subdirectory: 2 supporting mpi

As explained, PSyclone has the ability to support MPI parallelisation of the code. This is simply done by using the command line option `-dm` (instead of `-nodm`):

```
psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -dm -l output
        -opsy main_psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90 main_alg.x90
```

Use this option, and look at the PSy-layer. Some of the setup code has changed (which is related to getting the loop sizes based on a distributed field), and additionally there is now code that marks if the value of an array has changed, called `dirty`. This indicates that the neighbouring processes might not have the correct values, and these needs to be updated before they are used. The `set_dirty` calls themselves do not trigger any communication. This is only done when the modified values are actually used. In this example this happens in the user supplied kernel, which reads the data of `field_w0`. Look for the code that will trigger an update of the values of `field_w0`.

A small caveat: while this program could now be started with `mpirun`, there is no domain-decomposition done! So each copy would run the same code (each one computing the full field), since the fields are not distributed. This requires additional setup, which is beyond the scope of this tutorial.

Explanation

After initialising a field, it is marked to be modified (or 'dirty'):

```
DO df=loop0_start,loop0_stop
    field_3_proxy%data(df) = 0.0_r_def
END DO
!
! Set halos dirty/clean for fields modified in the above loop
!
CALL field_3_proxy%set_dirty()
```

Next time the fields are read, we need to get the newly computed values which might be on neighbouring processes. So the second subroutine in the PSy-layer contains:

```
IF (field_0_proxy%is_dirty(depth=1)) THEN
    CALL field_0_proxy%halo_exchange(depth=1)
END IF
!
DO cell=loop0_start,loop0_stop
    !
    CALL summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_code(nlayers,
        field_3_proxy%data, field_0_proxy%data, &
        ndf_w3, undf_w3, map_w3(:,cell), ndf_w0, &
```

```

                                undf_w0, map_w0(:,cell))
END DO
!
! Set halos dirty/clean for fields modified in the above loop
!
CALL field_3_proxy%set_dirty()

```

The halo-exchange uses an if-statement so that the communication functions are only called if the values of a field have actually changed. While in our case this is always be the case, in a more complex program it happens frequently that a field has not been updated since the last time the halo-values were exchanged. So this is an automatically applied optimisation that can significantly reduce the number of MPI calls required.

2.2.3 Applying OpenMP

Subdirectory 3 applying openmp

In this example you will add a transformation script to the PSyclone command line. This script will apply OpenMP transformation to the loops. Add the option `-s omp.py` to the PSyclone command, i.e.:

```

psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -s ./omp_transformation.py -
nodm -l output -opsy main_alg_psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90
main_alg.x90

```

The script will apply OpenMP parallelisation to all loops. Compare the PSy-layer files with the previously created files in the directory `../1_using_psyclone`. What has changed?

Optional: You can compile this example using `make compile`. Then set the environment variable `$OMP_NUM_THREADS` to an appropriate value and execute the compiled binary. The kernel will print out which thread number is executing which column indices. More explanations in [this] ([#explanation-for-applying-openmp](#)) section.

Explanation

You will see `omp parallel do` statements around each individual loop:

```

!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(df),
schedule(static)
DO df=loop0_start,loop0_stop
  field_3_proxy%data(df) = 0.0_r_def
END DO
!$omp end parallel do
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(df),
schedule(static)
DO df=loop1_start,loop1_stop
  field_0_proxy%data(df) = 1.0_r_def
END DO
!$omp end parallel do

```

While this example works, it is obviously very inefficient: the two loops should be in one `omp parallel` region, to avoid the overhead of stopping and starting the threads. This can be done in

PSyclone, but would require a slightly more complicated script.

For the user kernel you will see:

```
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(cell),
schedule(static)
DO cell=loop0_start,loop0_stop
!
CALL summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_code(nlayers, field_3_
proxy%data, field_0_proxy%data, &
ndf_w3, undf_w3,
map_w3(:,cell), &ndf_w0, undf_w0, map_w0(:,cell))
END DO
!$omp end parallel do
```

The optional task might print out:

```
Kernel executed by thread          1 of          3
using indices          16 -          20
Kernel executed by thread          1 of          3
using indices          21 -          25
Kernel executed by thread          1 of          3
using indices          26 -          30
Kernel executed by thread          0 of          3
using indices           1 -           5
Kernel executed by thread          0 of          3
using indices           6 -          10
Kernel executed by thread          0 of          3
using indices          11 -          15
Kernel executed by thread          2 of          3
using indices          31 -          35
Kernel executed by thread          2 of          3
using indices          36 -          40
Kernel executed by thread          2 of          3
using indices          41 -          45
```

A column is internally a section of a 1D-array. You can see in the output above that one column starts at index 16 and ends at index 20 etc.

2.2.4 MPI and OpenMP

Subdirectory: 4 mpi and openmp

This is an optional task and you can skip it if you are in a rush.

Especially for large models you would want to utilise hybrid parallelism, i.e. using MPI and OpenMP at the same time. In this example we will enable both kind of parallelisation at the same time. In order to do this, you need to invoke PSyclone with the `-dm` flag, but also apply the OpenMP transformation:

```
psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -s ./omp_transformation.py -dm
-l output -opsy main_al_psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90 main_
alg.x90
```

Again, check the created PSy-layer file `main_alg_psy.f90` for the calls to halo-exchanges and

OpenMP directives around loops. You can also compare it with the files created in directory `../2_supporting_mpi/`.

Explanation

Implementing hybrid parallelism is easy once a script was written to add the required OpenMP statements. The output file contains first the halo exchange, followed by the loop with OpenMP directives:

```

IF (field_0_proxy%is_dirty(depth=1)) THEN
  CALL field_0_proxy%halo_exchange(depth=1)
END IF
!
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(cell),
schedule(static)
DO cell=loop0_start,loop0_stop
  !
  CALL summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_code(nlayers, &
    field_3_proxy%data, field_0_proxy%data, &
    ndf_w3, undf_w3, map_w3(:,cell), &
    ndf_w0, undf_w0, map_w0(:,cell))
END DO
!$omp end parallel do
!
! Set halos dirty/clean for fields modified in the above
loop(s)
!
CALL field_3_proxy%set_dirty()

```

2.2.5 Error in Algorithm Layer

Subdirectory: 5 alg layer error

Now let's have a look at some typical errors. Ideally they should not happen for a user of a stable LFRic release, but if you for example should select an untested set of options some of these problems could still happen. The first example `main_alg.x90` contains an invalid PSyclone builtin name, though of course PSyclone cannot know what exactly the user meant. Use:

```

psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -nodm -l output -opsy main_alg_
psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90 main_alg.x90

```

Does PSyclone's error message make sense?

Explanation

PSyclone will print the following error message (or a variation of it, since depending on version the list of builtins might change):

```

Parse Error: kernel call 'no_setval_c' must either be named
in a use statement (found ['global_mesh_base_mod',
'mesh_mod', 'mesh_mod', 'partition_mod', ..., 'log_mod',

```

```
'summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_mod']) or be a recognised builtin (one of ['x_plus_y', 'inc_x_plus_y', 'a_plus_x', 'inc_a_plus_x', ... , 'real_x']) for this API)
```

PSyclone cannot know if `no_setval_c` is supposed to be a builtin (for which no use statement would be required), or if it is supposed to be a user-defined kernel (which requires a use statement).

2.2.6 Missing Parameter

Subdirectory: 6 missing parameter

This example misses a kernel parameter. Run PSyclone, i.e.:

```
psyclone --psykal-dsl lfriic -nodm -l output -opsy main_alg_psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90 main_alg.x90
```

What happens?

Explanation

```
PSyclone will detect that a parameter is missing for the kernel:
Parse Error: Kernel 'summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_type' called from the algorithm layer with an insufficient number of arguments as specified by the metadata. Expected at least '2' but found '1'.
```

PSyclone will verify the code the user asked to be created as much as possible and raise any issues early on, i.e. before even compiling the code.

2.2.7 Incorrect Naming Scheme

Subdirectory: 8 incorrect naming

This example shows the importance of naming the files correctly. It is basically the same code as in the very first PSyclone example, but the kernel file has been renamed to `summation_w0_to_w3_mod.f90`, while the module name is still `summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_mod` and the use statement in the algorithm layer is unchanged as well:

```
use summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_mod, only: summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_type
```

This works with a compiler (assuming that the kernel is compiled before the algorithm file), since the compiler will create a compiler-specific file `summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_mod`, which stores the required information about this module. PSyclone does not have this information, and as such relies on the naming scheme for finding the source files for modules. Therefore, PSyclone cannot find the source file for the kernel, and since the data in this kernel specifies which kind of loop to create, it cannot process the algorithm layer.

Run PSyclone with the standard command:

```
psyclone --psykal-dsl lfric -dm -l output -opsy main_alg_
psy.f90 -oalg main_alg.f90 main_alg.x90
```

and look at the error message provided by PSyclone.

Explanation

PSyclone will print the error message:

```
Parse Error: Kernel file 'summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_mod.
[fF]90' not found in
.../training/users/lfric/8_incorrect_naming
```

Notice that the error message exactly specifies the file name PSyclone is looking for, and also in which directory it is searching. PSyclone provides the command line parameter `-d` to specify a directory in which kernels will be searched. In this case you could add `-d ../1_` using `using_psyclone` and the kernel would be found in the first example.

3. PSyclone Domains

This section introduces the concept of PSyclone domains. Details about the two supported domains LFRic and GOcean are presented. Since most of the training material will be done with the GOcean domain, the focus is on the Gocean domain, and the corresponding infrastructure library `dl_esm_inf` is introduced.

There is no hands-on session for this part.

3.1 PSyclone Domains - Slides

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PSyclone Code Creation

- PSyclone uses the concept of a domain (or API) to know what code to create
- For each domain a specific infrastructure library is used
 - This library provides
 - Fields
 - Grid or meshes
 - Functionality for distributed memory operations
 - The infrastructure library is typically implemented using MPI, PSyclone itself does only call this well-defined interface

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LFRic Domain

- Unstructured grid
- One loop (over all cells in the 2D mesh) over all elements
- Each element is a column of the 3D grid
 - Each kernel must operate on a column, i.e. typically contains a loop over the vertical
- Infrastructure library is part of LFRic
 - Check `lfric_core` repository, `infrastructure/source` subdirectory
 - PSyclone contains a stripped-down version of this infrastructure library (e.g. no MPI support)
 - Sufficient for unit testing, examples, and training

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GOcean Domain

- Regular 2D grid
 - Knows about staggered grids, supports Arakawa C
- Two nested loops
 - all rows
 - All cells in a row
- Each kernel computes a single element, i.e. one index in a field array
- Infrastructure library dl_esm_inf
 - Daresbury Laboratory Earth-System Modelling Infrastructure library
https://github.com/stfc/dl_esm_inf
 - Provides various grid types
 - Supports MPI parallelisation

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Any Kernel Needs Additional Information

- LFRic: which column to compute
 - A field is actually a 1D array
 - A kernel needs to know which elements of this 1D field to compute
 - A rather complex set of rules to indicate these implicit arguments

```

loop0_start = 1
loop0_stop = mesh%get_last_halo_cell(1)
! Loop over 2D mesh:
DO cell=loop0_start,loop0_stop
  CALL testkern_w0_code(nlayers, field1_data, ..., &
    map_w0(:,cell))
END DO
    
```

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Any Kernel Needs Additional Information

- GOcean: which element to compute
 - A field is a 2D array
 - A kernel gets two indices i and j


```

DO j = a_fld%whole%ystart, a_fld%whole%ystop, 1
  DO i = a_fld%whole%xstart, a_fld%whole%xstop, 1
    CALL update_field_code(i, j, a_fld%data, ...)
  END DO
END DO
    
```

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Next Steps

- We start with using the GOcean API
 - It's a lot easier to understand because it avoids the complex handling required for finite elements
 - The additional, automatically added arguments are a lot easier to understand
- We will implement a simple code first using `dl_esm_inf` to get used to the library
- Then we will re-implement this code using PSyclone to create the loops
- Start to look at code transformations

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DL_ESM_INF
 Daresbury Laboratory
 Earth-System Modelling
 Infrastructure library

https://github.com/stfc/dl_esm_inf

Introduction to DM_ESM_INF

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- Simple library to allow creation of grids and fields on these grids
- While in theory supports 3D grids and fields
 - Atm only 2D is fully supported
- Provides user-defined types for grids and fields
- Supports MPI parallelisation
 - When compiled with MPI support
 - Otherwise, all parallelisation related operations are no-ops
- Provides staggered grids
 - u, v, f are between t points
 - In the example to the right, u, v, f are to the south-west of t
- We will be using t points only

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Creating a Grid

```

USE grid_mod, only      : grid_type, GO_ARAKAWA_C, GO_BC_EXTERNAL, GO_OFFSET_SW
use parallel_mod, only  : parallel_init

TYPE(grid_type), target :: grid

call parallel_init()    ! Initialise MPI - if dl_esm_inf is compiled with MPI

! Create the information about the grid type to be used. We need to provide
! 3 boundary conditions ... here this will add halos, 3rd arg is ignored
grid = grid_type(GO_ARAKAWA_C, (/GO_BC_EXTERNAL,GO_BC_EXTERNAL,GO_BC_EXTERNAL/), &
                GO_OFFSET_SW)

! Grid has n_cols * n_rows points in one domain (i.e. one process), halo size is 1
call grid%decompose(n_cols, n_rows, ndomains=1, halo_width=1)

! Create an equidistant grid:
call grid_init(grid, dxarg=1.0_8, dyarg=1.0_8)
    
```

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Creating and Using a Field

```

USE field_mod, only      : r2d_field, GO_T_POINTS
TYPE(r2d_field)         :: neighbours

neighbours = r2d_field(grid, GO_T_POINTS)

neighbours%data(i, j) = neighbours%data(i, j) + 1

-----
! To distribute global data to domain decomposition:
real(kind=8), dimension(:,:), allocatable :: initial_state
...
initial = r2d_field(grid, grid_points = GO_T_POINTS, &
                  init_global_data = initial_state)
    
```


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4. The Game of Life

This section introduces Conway's Game of Life. The Game of Life (GoL) is used as example in most of this training material. As this section shows, the code required to implement GoL is very similar to numerical simulation codes: it has different kernels, and uses stencil accesses.

The hands-on session will focus on getting more familiar with the GOcean infrastructure library `dl_esm_inf`. It will be used to implement a first version of the GoL, before re-implementing it later with PSyclone.

4.1 The Game of Life - Slides

Game of Life

Our example application

This slide features a blue brain icon in the top left corner and a blue gradient bar in the top right corner. The text is centered on a white background.

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Game of Life

- Simple cellular automaton
 - 2D finite grid structure
 - Each cell has 8 neighbours
 - Rules to compute the next state ('generation') based on current generation
- Developed by mathematician John Conway in 1970
 - Cellular automata first described 1940s by Stanislaw Ulam and John von Neumann
 - Made well known by Martin Gardner in a 1970 Scientific American article
- Initial state given by user
 - Computer then computes the next generation
- For geeks: Game of Life is Turing complete
 - I.e. a Game of Life board can simulate any computations
 - Implemented using logic gates

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This slide features a red 'OFFICIAL' label in the top right, a blue gradient bar in the top right, and a blue brain icon in the bottom right. The text is left-aligned on a white background.

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Game of Life: Rules

- Played on a rectangular 2d grid of cells
- Each cell has two states:
 - Live or dead
- If a live cell has less than 2 or more than 3 neighbours, it dies because of loneliness or overpopulation
 - Otherwise, the cell stays live
- If a dead cell has exactly 3 live neighbours, it becomes a live cell by reproduction
 - Otherwise, it stays dead

IN THE YEAR 2024, MANY AREAS OF PHYSICS RESEARCH STILL USE THE FORTRAN PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE

"IN 2024, ARE YOU KIDDING ME?"

PHYSICISTS

It's a peaceful life.

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Example configurations

- Stable configurations

	■	■	■	
	■	■	■	

		■			
	■	■	■		
		■			

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Cylic Configurations

- Period 2:

- Many other exist, with longer periods as well

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Spaceships/Glider

- There are 'gun' shapes, that constantly emit gliders
 - Kind of electric signal. A stream of gliders can then be inverted, and'ed, or'ed etc

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Implementing Game of Life Using dl_esm_inf

- Get initial state (e.g. read from config file) into CURRENT state
- Compute number of neighbours in NEIGHBOURS
- Compute newborn cells in BORN
 - $CURRENT == 0 \ \&\& \ NEIGHBOURS == 3 \rightarrow BORN = 1$
- Compute dying cells in DIED
 - $CURRENT == 1 \ \&\& \ (NEIGHBOURS < 2 \text{ or } NEIGHBOURS > 3) \rightarrow DIE = 1$
- Update state:
 - $CURRENT = CURRENT + BORN - DIE$

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Comparison with Real HPC Code

- NEMO

```
do jk =
  do jj =
    do ji =
      zwt(ji,jj) = ( ff_t(ji,jj) * e1e2t(ji,jj) + pv(ji,jj,jk) ...
```

- Similar structure to die/born computation

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Counting Neighbours: Stencil Access

- Example for stencil: 1d heat equation
 - $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2}$
 - $\frac{u(t+dt, x) - u(t, x)}{dt} = \frac{u(t, x+dx) - 2u(t, x) + u(t, x-dx)}{dx^2}$
 - $u(t + dt, x) = u(t, x) + dt \frac{u(t, x+dx) - 2u(t, x) + u(t, x-dx)}{dx^2}$
 - $u_new(i) = u(i) + dt * (u(i+1) + 2 * u(i) + u(i-1)) / dx ** 2$
- Discretisation
Solve for $u(t+dt, x)$
- Similar access to counting neighbours:
 - ! Count the neighbours that are alive
 - neighbours(i, j) = c(i-1, j-1) + c(i, j-1) + c(i+1, j-1) &
 + c(i-1, j) + c(i+1, j) &
 + c(i-1, j+1) + c(i, j+1) + c(i+1, j+1)

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Game of Life Implementation

- Main program `go1.f90`
 - Get config file name and call `read_config_mod`
 - Call `time_step_mod` for time-stepping and output.
- `read_config_mod.f90`
 - Initialises `dl_esm_inf`
 - Reads config file given on command line
Using a 2d global Fortran array `initial_state`
 - Creates the local initial state `initial` as a r2d field using the global `initial_state`
 - `dl_esm_inf` will distribute the data for you
 - Though with single process that's just a copy operation

Config file for a glider:

```
# 10x10 grid, 20 time steps
10 10 20
1 1
1 3
2 2
2 3
3 2
```


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Game of Life Implementation

- `Time_step_mod.f90`

```
do time =1, time_steps
  call count_neighbours
  call compute_born
  call compute_die
  call combine
  call output_field(current)
enddo
```


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Boundary Conditions

- Counting neighbours requires tests at the edge of the grid
 - If $i > 1$: $\text{count} = \text{count} + \text{state}(i-1, j)$
- Bad for performance ☹️
- Instead, add a row/columns around the area, which is set to 0
 - Halo cells, ghost cells
- This area would be used to set boundary conditions in a simulation
- This is done automatically when creating the grid
 - Each field on our grid will have the specified halo

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Where is dl_esm_inf?

- Initialisation done in `read_config_mod`
 - Contains most of the code
- Creating a field, e.g.:
`neighbours = r2d_field(grid, GO_T_POINTS)`
- For distributed memory:
 - Call to exchange halos (details later)
 - Output contains a call to gather local data into one array
- Access of field data:
`neighbours%data(i, j) = neighbours%data(i, j) + 1`
- The `dl_esm_inf` API, on which PSyclone relies, provides these functions (fields, halo exchange, grid, %data)

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Setting up PSyclone

```
module load python3/3.12.1 python3-as-python
git clone --recurse-submodules -b 1623_add_training
https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone.git
cd PSyclone
# git submodule init
# git submodule update
python3 -m venv venv
source ./venv/bin/activate
module load gcc/12.2.0 openmpi netcdf/4.9.2
python3 -m pip install .
# pip3 install Jinja2 ← that should not be necessary anymore
cd tutorial/training/gocean/2.2-GameOfLife
```

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Hands-on 2.2

- Finish the Game of Life implementation using `DL_ESM_INF`
- 2.2-GameOfLife contains template
- For you to do:
 - In `timestep_mod.f90`: declare the fields for *die* and *born*, and create them.
 - Add the parameters to the various kernels
 - First parameter is always output (coding style), you need to check with the actual kernels for the order otherwise
 - Finish `compute_die_mod.f90`
 - Finish `compute_born_mod.f90`
 - Finish `combine_mod.f90`
 - Finish `count_neighbours_mod.f90`

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Compiling and Running

- Compilation can be done using `make`
- Two config files are contained in
 - `../gol_lib/config.glider` and `../gol_lib/config.glider-large`
 - The first one is used in testing, prints grid after each time step
 - The second is a larger example (1000x1000 grid, 2000 time steps)
 - No output
- You can run the example using `make run`
or `./gol ../gol_lib/config.glider`
- A simple test can be run using `make test`
- Each directory has a `solution` subdirectory
 - It contains all finished files, you can compile and run in these directories
 - you can run `make/make test` there

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4.2 Introduction to dl_esm_inf

Directory: PScyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.2-GameOfLife

This tutorial introduces the infrastructure library `dl_esm_inf`, which is used by the PScyclone GOcean API. As example we will implement Conway's 'Game of Life'. This directory contains templates for the functions, but you need to add code to various files. Work through these insrtuctions, which will guide you through all required changes.

Game of Life is a cellular automaton developed by John Conway in 1970. It is a set of four simple rules which determine how cells develop on a simple 2d grid. Given is an initial state defining which cells in the grid are alive. Then the following rules are applied:

- If a live cell has less than 2 live neighbours, it dies (under-population).
- If a live cell has more than 3 live neighbours, it dies (overpopulation).
- Any dead cell with exactly three live neighbours becomes a live cell (reproduction).
- Any life or dead cell for which none of the previous rules applies, will stay the way it is (i.e. either live or dead).

Neighbour includes the diagonals, so a cell has eight neighbours.

There is a huge variety of cellular automata, some of which are easy to analyse, some of which are more complex. The Game of Life has been shown to be a Universal Turing Machine (UTM) meaning that you can create initial conditions that allows you to do any computations just by following these rules (see the wikipedia entries for *Game of Life* and UTM for precise definitions).

Implementation

In the spirit of numerical analysis the grid is represented by a 2D double precision array (main reason for using double precision is that the infrastructure library at this stage only provides double precision fields). Each live cell is stored as a '1', each dead cell as a '0'. We use the following algorithm:

1. Compute a field neighbour which stores the number of live neighbours for each cell. Note that the halo is used to store the boundary conditions.
2. Compute a field die based on the current cell state and number of neighbours, and stores a '1' for each live cell that dies due to under- or over-population.
3. Compute a field born based on the current cell state and number of neighbours, which stores a '1' for each dead cell that will create a new cell due to reproduction.
4. Update the current state by adding the born field and subtracting the die field.

This is then repeated for the number of required time steps.

A configuration file is used to store the initial configuration. It has the following format (see `../gol-lib/config.glider`):

```
# 10x10 grid, 20 time steps
10 10 20
1 1
1 3
```

The first line is a comment line and is always ignored. The second line contains the number of columns, number of rows, and number of steps. This is then followed by a list of coordinates of cells that are alive - column row format.

The following sections describes the required changes in the files.

4.2.1 Reading in the configuration: `read_config.f90`

This subroutine takes the name of the configuration file to use from the first and only command line parameter. It will read the grid size from the configuration file. The grid size is then used to initialise the `dl_esm_inf` grid object. This happens in four steps:

1. Initialise the parallelisation subsystem with a call to `parallel_init`.
2. Create an Arakawa-C grid by constructing the grid object with the `grid_type` constructor. The `grid_type` constructor takes three parameters: the first one the grid type (`GO_ARAKAWA_C`, the only one currently supported by `dl_esm_inf` and `PSyclone`), a 3D array indicating the boundary conditions for each dimension - use `GO_BC_EXTERNAL`, and the offset as `GO_OFFSET_SW`.
3. Now the domain decomposition can be specified. The `decompose` method of the grid object constructed in the previous step can just take the number of domains, which is 1 in this case. Also use a halo region of 1, which will be used to store 0 and avoid tests when counting neighbours.
4. Finally the grid initialisation can be called, providing the distance between grid points. We do not need this information, so just call `grid_init` with the grid parameter, and `dxarg=1.0, dy_arg=1.0`.

Once the grid has been properly created and initialised, we read in the config file (`get_initial_state`), which will store the initial state from the config file in the Fortran array `initial_state`. This Fortran array can then be used to initialise the actual field with this value.

While this could be combined in one step, this implementation will later allow us to use distributed memory without additional change, since the `rd2_field` constructor will take care of the data distribution.

4.2.2 The main program: `gol.f90`

As is obvious from the previous step, the main program does not have to do much with `dl_esm_inf` - it just passes the grid that is initialised in `read_config.f90` to the function `time_step.f90`.

4.2.3 Time-stepping: `time_step_mod.f90`

The time stepping function receives the initial state of the cells as parameters and uses it as

5. Game of Life in PSyclone

This section describes the re-implementation of the Game of Life using PSyclone. This section first introduces the concept of a kernel. It first describes the meta-data required in the specification of a kernel, then shows how a kernel is called. It finishes with the command line options required for processing files with PSyclone.

The hands-on session will then show how to implement the Game of Life with PSyclone

5.1 Game of Life in PSyclone

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Implementing GoL with PSyclone

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Kernel Definition

- In order for PSyclone to create the right kernel call, it needs to know about the parameters a kernel expects
 - As we will see PSyclone needs to know the iteration space (internal, halo, or all points)
 - Access pattern
- This is called the **meta-data** of a kernel
- This is done by defining a special user-defined type in a kernel file
 - This type is never used in Fortran code
 - But it is parsed by PSyclone to get information about the kernel
- Why a user-defined type?
 - So we can parse using an existing Fortran parser ☺

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Example Kernel

```

module compute_die_mod
use kernel_mod, only: GO_INTERNAL_PTS, GO_POINTWISE, &
                    kernel_type
use argument_mod, only: go_arg, GO_CT, GO_READ, GO_WRITE
use grid_mod, only: GO_OFFSET_SW

type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args = &
(/ go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
 go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
 go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) /) &
!> This kernel writes to all internal points
!! of the simulation domain.
integer :: ITERATES_OVER = GO_INTERNAL_PTS
integer :: INDEX_OFFSET = GO_OFFSET_SW
contains
procedure, nopass :: code => compute_die_code
end type compute_die
contains
...
end module compute_die_mod
    
```


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Example Module File with a Kernel

```

module compute_die_mod
...
type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
...
end type compute_die

contains

subroutine ...
end subroutine ...

end module compute_die_mod
    
```

Module name follows naming conventions

Defines the name of this kernel

The type contains the meta-data

- Remember the naming convention as explained in PSystem for users training, this kernel must be in file `compute_die_mod.f90`

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Kernel Arguments

```

use kernel_mod, only: GO_INTERNAL_PTS, GO_POINTWISE, &
                    kernel_type
use argument_mod, only: go_arg, GO_CT, GO_READ, GO_WRITE
use grid_mod, only: GO_OFFSET_SW

type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
  type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args =
  (/ go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) /) &

```

Importing the required symbols from dl_esm_inf

Defines arguments of the kernel as an array

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Argument Declarations

1. Access mode (read, write etc):
 - GO_READ, GO_WRITE, GO_READWRITE
 - GO_INC, GO_MAX, GO_MIN, GO_SUM
2. Type
 - Fields: GO_CT, GO_CU, GO_CV, GO_CF
 - Scalars: GO_R_SCALAR, GO_I_SCALAR
 - Grid properties: GO_GRID_AREA_T, GO_GRID_DX_U
3. Stencil access
 - GO_POINTWISE: only the current indices are used, required for scalars (on our todo list)!
 - GO_STENCIL: a stencil access (see next slide)
 - Missing for grid properties

```

go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE)
go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE)
go_arg(GO_READ, GO_R_SCALAR, GO_POINTWISE)
go_arg(GO_READ, GO_GRID_AREA_T)
go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_STENCIL(...))

```

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Stencil Access

- Stencil accesses are accesses to neighbouring indices.
- Example from 1D heat equation:

$$u_{\text{new}}(i) = u(i) + dt * (u(i+1) + 2 * u(i) + u(i-1)) / dx * dx$$
- Example from GoL:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{neighbours}(i, j) = & c(i-1, j-1) + c(i, j-1) + c(i+1, j-1) \\ & + c(i-1, j) + c(i, j) + c(i+1, j) \\ & + c(i-1, j+1) + c(i, j+1) + c(i+1, j+1) \end{aligned}$$
- Using the distance in each direction, this is represented by:

1	1	1
1		1
1	1	1

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GO_STENCIL

- The stencil can then be written as:

1	1	1
1		1
1	1	1
- To declare this in PSystem, use GO_STENCIL with three integers (including leading zeros if required):


```
go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_STENCIL(111, &
                                     101, &
                                     111))
```

 - Values can be larger than one to indicate 'longer' stencils (e.g. i+2)
- Incidentally:


```
GO_POINTWISE = GO_STENCIL(000, 010, 000)
```

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Remaining Meta-Data

```

type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
  type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args =
  ...
  !> This kernel writes to all internal points
  !! of the simulation domain.
  integer :: ITERATES_OVER = GO_INTERNAL_PTS
  integer :: INDEX_OFFSET = GO_OFFSET_SW
contains
  procedure, nopass :: code => compute_die_code
end type compute_die
contains

```

ITERATES_OVER: This kernel computes all internal points (i.e. not halo or boundary condition). Also: ALL and EXTERNAL

INDEX_OFFSET: the direction in which u,v,f points are

CODE: the name of the subroutine that implements the actual kernel

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Example Kernel

```

use kernel_mod, only: GO_INTERNAL_PTS, GO_POINTWISE, &
  kernel_type
use argument_mod, only: go_arg, GO_CT, GO_READ, GO_WRITE
use grid_mod, only: GO_OFFSET_SW

type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
  type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args =
  (/ go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), &
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) /) &
  !> This kernel writes to all internal points
  !! of the simulation domain.
  integer :: ITERATES_OVER = GO_INTERNAL_PTS
  integer :: index_offset = GO_OFFSET_SW
contains
  procedure, nopass :: code => compute_die_code
end type compute_die
contains

```

Importing the required symbols from dl_esm_inf

Extends a dl_esm provided kernel_type. Defines name of the kernel

Declaring code to be the actual subroutine of the kernel implementation

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Kernel Implementation

```

type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
  type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args = &
    (/ go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) &
     go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) &
     go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) /) &
contains
  procedure, nopass :: code => compute_die_code
end type compute_die

contains
!> @param[in] i, j Coordinates of the cell to update.
!> @param[out] die The output field with 1 iff the cell dies.
!> @param[in] current The current state.
!> @param[in] neighbours The number of live neighbours for each cell.
subroutine compute_die_code(i, j, die, current, neighbours)
  double precision, dimension(:, :), intent(out) :: die
  double precision, dimension(:, :), intent(in) :: current, neighbours
  integer, intent(in) :: i, j
  die(i, j) = 0.0
  if (current(i, j) > 0.0 .and. (neighbours(i, j) < 3.0) ) &
    die(i, j) = 1.0
end subroutine compute_die_code
    
```

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Explicit parameters as declared in the meta-data

Fields become 2D Fortran arrays

Implicit parameters giving the index to work on

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Parameters of a Kernel

- First two integer parameter which are the indices of the element to compute
- Then the parameters declared in the meta-data
 - Same order
- Each field will be provided as a 2D Fortran array!
 - PSyclone will provide the data from the field type to the kernel
- Scalar will be provided as is
- Grid properties can have various types
See <https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/gocean1p0.html#id2>

Name	Description	Type
go_grid_area_t	Cell area at T point	Real array, rank=2
go_grid_mask_t	T-point mask (1=wet, 0=dry)	Integer array, rank=2
go_grid_x_min_index	Minimum X index	Integer, scalar

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Implementing a Kernel

- Declare the meta-data for the kernel
- Implement the subroutine
 - Adding two additional integer arguments for the indices
- Fields become 2D arrays
- Scalars are just scalars
- Grid properties need to be appropriately declared
- The indices to use will be provided by PSyclone
 - Since PSyclone will create the loops over all elements for you
- No need to write any loops, just compute for the given indices
 - The kernels will be shorter because of that.
 - Except that you also need to specify meta-data ☹

**WHEN YOU LOOK AT
CODE YOU WROTE LAST YEAR**

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Discussing Meta-Data

- There is some information duplication between meta-data and subroutine parameters:
 - Fortran `intent` vs `GO_READ`, `GO_WRITE`, `GO_READWRITE`
 - Though `GO_SUM/MAX/MIN` might be harder to detect
 - Stencil information could be automatically deduced from the access patterns
 - The functionality to collect variable access was added later, at some stage we will evaluate how to improve this (e.g. consistency check vs reduction of meta-data information required)
 - Can be quite complicated, e.g. consider:


```
iml = i-1
jpl=j+1
a(iml,jpl) = ...
```
- But grid parameters would still need to be specified somehow.

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To Call a Kernel

- The file must be processed by PSystem
- Use the meta-data type from the module
- Use `call invoke(...)` with the meta-data type and the required parameters
- Only provide the fields and scalars declared in the meta-data
 - PSystem will provide indices and grid data based on the first field

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Example Kernel Calls

- Simple call:

```
use compute_die_mod, only: compute_die
...
call invoke(compute_die(die, current, neighbours))
```
- Several kernel calls can be combined into one invoke:

```
call invoke(compute_die(die, current, neighbours), &
            compute_born(born, current, neighbours), ...)
```
- You can name invokes:

```
call invoke(compute_die(die, current, neighbours), &
            compute_born(born, current, neighbours), &
            name="compute_die_born")
```
- This looks to a compiler like calling a subroutine, with instances of the kernel types as parameter using a default constructor
 - it won't actually compile ☹

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Calling PSyclone

<code>\$ psyclone</code>	<code>\</code>	The psyclone command line script
<code>--psykal-dsl gocean</code>	<code>\</code>	The API/domain to create code for
<code>-l output</code>	<code>\</code>	Limited line length for output files to 132 characters
<code>-nodm</code>	<code>\</code>	No distributed memory support
<code>-oalg time_step_alg_mod.f90</code>	<code>\</code>	Output filename for rewritten algorithm layer
<code>-opsy time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90</code>	<code>\</code>	Output filename for created PSy-layer
<code>time_step_alg_mod.x90</code>		Name of the file to process

Note: prior to 3.0: use `-api` instead of `--psykal-dsl`

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Hands-on 2.4 – Part 1

- tutorial/training/gocean
- Finish the implementation of `compute_die` kernel
 - Meta-data etc already done, you only need to implement the code
- Add the meta-data for `compute_born`
 - Arguments, `iterates_over`, `index_offset`
- Add the meta-data for `combine_mod`
 - Take care of the arguments, not all are just read/write
- Add the meta-data for `count_neighbours`
 - As above, but be aware that this uses a stencil access

- You can check at least for syntactic correctness by using the compiler:
`make compute_die_mod.o`

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Hands-on 2.4, Part 2

1. Replace the calls in `time_step_alg_mod.x90` with invokes
 1. Use one invoke for each call
 2. Use one invoke to contain some calls
 3. Use one invoke to contain all calls
2. In each case, process the files with PSyclone:
 - Using 'make' should work (though it will compile everything), you can also just use:


```
psyclone --psykal-dsl gocean -l output -nodm \
          --config /home/joerg/work/psyclone/config/psyclone.cfg \
          -oalg time_step_alg_mod.f90 \
          -opsy time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90 time_step_alg_mod.x90
```
 - In each case check the differences in the created algorithm layer file `time_step_alg_mod.f90`, and the subroutines created in `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90`
3. Use `make run` and `make test` to check if everything works as expected

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Setting up PSyclone

```
$ module load python3/3.12.1 python3-as-python
$ git clone --recurse-submodules -b 1623_add_training \
  https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone.git
$ module load gcc/12.2.0 openmpi netcdf/4.9.2
$ cd PSyclone
# git submodule init      # if you didn't --recurse-submodules
# git submodule update
$ python3 -m venv venv
$ source ./venv/bin/activate
$ python3 -m pip install .
# pip3 install jinja2    ← that should not be necessary anymore
$ cd tutorial/training/gocean/2.4-GameOfLife-psyclone
README nicer version:
https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone/tree/1623\_add\_training/tutorial/training/gocean/2.4-GameOfLife-psyclone
```

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Overview

- Game of Life rules:
 - Each cell has two states: Live (1) or dead (0)
 - A live cell with less than 2 or more than 3 neighbours dies
 - A dead cell has exactly 3 live neighbours becomes a live cell
- Compilation can be done using `make`
- Two config files are contained in
 - `../gol_lib/config.glider` and `../gol_lib/config.glider-large`
- You can run the example using `make run`
or `./gol ../gol_lib/config.glider`
- A simple test can be run using `make test`
- Each directory has a `solution` subdirectory
 - It contains all finished files, you can compile and run in these directories
 - you can run `make/make test` there

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Summary

- Introduction to Game of Life
- How PSystem code creation works conceptually
- Meta-data declaration for GOcean
- Writing kernels for GOcean
 - Using implicit arguments
- Calling kernels
 - Differences in code creation when combining several kernel calls in one invoke

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5.2 Game of Line in Psyclone - Hands-on

Directory: PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.4-GameOfLife-psyclone

The goal of this exercise is to re-implement the Game of Life using PSyclone. The implementation will closely follow the design of the previous session: we use `dl_esm_inf` and especially the field type provided to implement the 2d arrays. And again we compute first the number of neighbours, then based on the current state and number of neighbours we compute if a cell dies, or a new one is born, before combining these fields. But these functions will now become kernels that operate on a single element, and PSyclone will create the loop structures automatically.

A word about coding style: we will follow the LFRic coding style, which is documented on <https://code.metoffice.gov.uk/trac/lfric/wiki/LFRicTechnical/FortranCodingStandards> (login required). This requires that any module name is the same as the filename (and typically has a suffix of `_mod`). Any file that needs to be processed by PSyclone, i.e. it contains `invoke` statements, uses the extensions `.x90`. Additionally, the filename should contain `_alg`. For example, the time stepping module in the Game of Life will be called `time_step_alg_mod.x90`. This is in no way required or enforced by PSyclone itself (all filename need to be specified with extensions), and you can define your own coding style.

This tutorial starts by implementing the various kernels before implementing the actual `invoke` calls. Note that the kernels need to be declared (i.e. at least their meta-data needs to be available) before you can run PSyclone, even for simple tests.

Note that it is not possible to verify kernel meta-data. Only when PSyclone is running on the algorithm layer with the `invoke` statements will the kernel declarations be read and interpreted.

5.2.1 Implement `compute_die` kernel

We start with implementing the `compute_die` kernel. It is contained the `compute_die_mod.f90` file. Note that only the algorithm layers are processed by PSyclone, so there is no need for the kernel files to use the `.x90` extension. PSyclone will read the kernel files when creating the algorithm layer. This file already contains the meta-data information for the kernel:

```
private
public compute_die, compute_die_code
type, extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die
    type(go_arg), dimension(3) :: meta_args =
        (/go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), & !
field
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE), & !
field
    go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE) & !
field
    /)
!> This kernel writes to all points of the
!! simulation domain.
integer :: ITERATES_OVER = GO_INTERNAL_PTS
integer :: index_offset = GO_OFFSET_SW

contains
```

```
procedure, nopass :: code => compute_die_code
end type compute_die
```

As explained, PSyclone will read this type information that specified the meta-data for the kernel. It looks like a standard Fortran type declaration, and as such can be compiled with any compiler, but the type itself is not used, it is only used to provide the meta-data to PSyclone. Still, the type and the kernel function need to be declared to be public, otherwise a compilation error will be triggered.

As a a reminder, here the details of this declaration:

- The kernel is called `compute_die` based on the line type, `extends(kernel_type) :: compute_die`.
- The kernel takes three arguments (`dimension(3)`). The first argument will be the field containing cells that die, the second argument the current status of all cells, and the last the number of neighbours.
- The first argument is written, and it is a field on the T-space and is used pointwise (i.e. only using the coordinates (i,j)).
- The second and third arguments are both read-only, on the CT-space and used pointwise.
- It iterates over the internal points, i.e. does not handle any points on a halo or boundary layer.
- Index offset is South-West.
- The subroutine that contains the kernel is called `compute_die_code`.

Todo

There is no need to modify this meta-data, it has been correctly filled out for you. But the body of the actual kernel code (`compute_die_code`) is missing. Implement this code, and remember that you only need to write code for the single element (i,j) (i and j are parameters passed in by PSyclone). Remember that the output field needs to be initialised with zero here (since it will contain the result from the previous iteration otherwise).

5.2.2 Implement the `compute_born` kernel

As you might remember from the exercise 2.2, this kernel takes three arguments, first an output field that stores which entries will get a new, alive cell, and two input parameters specifying the current state and the number of neighbours for each cell.

In the template for this function, you only need to add the declaration of the parameters in the meta data. You can use the previous kernel as template.

5.2.3 Implement the `combine` kernel

This template file is nearly empty. You need to add the full meta-data declaration (make sure to declare the type and the actual function called to be public), and the kernel code. Again, feel free to use the previous kernel as example.

5.2.4 Implement the `count_neighbours` kernel

This is the last kernel that needs to be implemented. While the kernel takes only one output parameter (number of neighbours) and one input parameter (current state), there is one big difference compared with any other kernel: this kernel accesses the current state as a stencil, i.e. it does not (only) read `current(i, j)`, but also accesses the neighbours. The meta-data for this kernel must declare this access (which will later be important in case of a distributed memory implementation, and when applying certain transformations). So the access for the input field is not `GO_POINTWISE`, but it has to be declared as `GO_STENCIL`, and the parameter specifying the extend in each direction in which neighbouring elements are accessed. The stencil declaration (which is used instead of `GO_POINTWISE`) looks like this:

```
GO_STENCIL(010,    &
           010,    &
           010))
```

for a field that accesses elements one row above and below. Adjust this declaration to the access pattern used when counting the neighbours. The template for `count_neighbours` contains some of the meta-data and the full implementation. Finish the declaration of the meta-data. Note that at this stage PSyclone does not verify the stencil declaration with the actual code, but it is on the todo list of the PSyclone developers.

You also need to implement the actual kernel for `count_neighbours`, i.e. adding up the values of the 8 neighbours.

5.2.5 Update `time_step_mod`

Now that all kernels have been implemented, we can update the time step function `time_step_alg_mod.x90`. Insert the missing `invoke` statements and the required parameters (you might need to check with the kernel meta-data to make sure you have the parameters in the right order).

5.2.6 Use PSyclone

Now you run PSyclone to see if it correctly processes all your kernels. You can use the following command line:

```
psyclone -nodm --psykal-dsl gocean
         -oalg time_step_alg_mod.f90
         -opsy time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90
         time_step_alg_mod.x90
```

The flag `-nodm` disables distributed memory processing. We need to specify which PSyclone API we are using (`gocean`, which is the 2D finite difference one based on `dl_esm_inf`). Then the output filename for the algorithm layer (`-oalg`) and the psy layer files (`-opsy`) and the input filename.

The provided Makefile already contains a stand-alone target to do this for you:

```
make time_step_alg_mod.f90
```

If you get an error message, check the syntax of the `invoke` statement and the kernels. It can sometimes be useful to compile the algorithm or kernel file with a compiler, which might give

easier to understand error messages, for example:

```
gfortran -I ../external/PSyclone/external/dl_esm_inf/finite_
difference/src/
-c ./combine_mod.f90
```

Once PSyclone has successfully processed all the files, look at the algorithm- and psy-layer file PSyclone has created, i.e. `time_step_alg_mod.f90` and `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90`.

Here the changes that PSyclone has applied to the file `time_step_alg_mod.x90` in the newly created algorithm-layer file `time_step_alg_mod.f90`. Note that this file will not contain any comments, and the layout of the code will be different.

```
USE psy_time_step_alg_mod, ONLY: invoke_3_combine
USE psy_time_step_alg_mod, ONLY: invoke_2_compute_die
USE psy_time_step_alg_mod, ONLY: invoke_1_compute_born
USE psy_time_step_alg_mod, ONLY: invoke_0_count_neighbours
```

It has added use statements for the subroutines in the psy-layer file. Then it has also replaced the invoke statements with normal Fortran calls:

```
DO time = 1, time_steps
  CALL invoke_0_count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  CALL invoke_1_compute_born(born, current, neighbours)
  CALL invoke_2_compute_die(die, current, neighbours)
  CALL invoke_3_combine(current, die, born)
  IF (time_steps <= 20) CALL output_field(current)
END DO
```

You can find these newly created subroutines in the psy-layer file `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90`. For example, it contains the subroutine to count the neighbours:

```
MODULE psy_time_step_alg_mod
  USE field_mod
  USE kind_params_mod
  IMPLICIT NONE
  CONTAINS
  SUBROUTINE invoke_0_count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
    TYPE(r2d_field), intent(inout) :: neighbours
    TYPE(r2d_field), intent(inout) :: current
    INTEGER j
    INTEGER i

    DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,
neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
      DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
        CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
current%data)
      END DO
    END DO

  END SUBROUTINE invoke_0_count_neighbours
```

The subroutine contains the nested loop across all inner points, and calls the corresponding kernel function `count_neighbour_code`. It adds the parameters `i` and `j` for the element to use, and passes the plain 2d-Fortran arrays (and not the full fields) to the kernel by accessing the

%data member of the field parameters. If everything is done correctly, you can compile this example using:

```
make
```

and a binary `gol` will be created. You can run this with:

```
./gol ../gol-lib/config.glider
```

This is a small configuration with just 20 time steps, and the time stepping loop will display the grid after each step:

```
1.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.1.1.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
1.1.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
...
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.1.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.1.1.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.1.1.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.0.
```

You can see that the glider configuration is moving to the bottom right. To test if your implementation is correct, you can use

```
make test
```

This will run the small test, and compare the output of each time step with a known-good outcome contained in the file `glider.correct`:

```
./gol ../gol-lib/config.glider | tail -n 12 | diff - ./glider.correct
```

If no output is shown the results are correct, otherwise you will see the output from `diff`, e.g.:

```
9c9
< 0.0.0.0.0.1.1.0.0.0.
---
> 0.0.0.0.1.1.1.0.0.0.
```

If you measure the performance of this code, it will run significant slower than the original non-PSyclone version, especially if you are using `gfortran`. We will look at the

performance in the next tutorial.

5.2.7 Compacting the invoke calls

PSyclone can call more than one kernel in a invoke statement by just specifying more than one kernel call, each separated by commas:

```
call invoke(count_neighbours(neighbours, current), &  
           compute_born(born, current, neighbours), ...
```

Modify your `time_step_alg_mod.x90` file to use only one `invoke` statement, and call all four kernels. Then run PSyclone again, and look at the created algorithm file `time_step_alg_mod.f90`.

Combining several kernel calls into one `invoke` means that the loops are all in the same subroutine, which will allow code optimisations both automatically by the compiler, as well as using PSyclone.

5.2.8 Performance Check

Run the large configuration (which is a 1000x1000 grid with 2000 time steps), and compare the performance with the previous version that did not combine the calls, and with the original non-PSyclone version of the code.

6. PSyclone Internals

This section describes PSyclone's internal processing and representation of a program. It starts with explaining the parsing process using `fparser`, and then describes how the parse tree information is converted to PSyIR, the PSyclone Internal Representation.

There is no hands-on session for this part.

How PSyclone Works

1. Fortran Parsing

<https://code.metoffice.gov.uk/trac/jumps/wiki/NG-UJX>

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Handling Input Source Code

- Two-step process:
 1. Read in source code, and convert to abstract syntax tree representing Fortran
 - An AST is a data structure that represents code
 2. Convert the AST into the PSyclone internal representation (PSyIR)
 - More specialised than AST, i.e. simpler representation
 - Makes use of meta-data

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Reading Fortran – fparser2

- A Fortran reader reads in the source code (part of fparser2)
 - Support for fixed and free format
- No support for pre-processing
 - Directives are just ignored
 - Some support for recognising omp/openacc directives
- This source code is then converted into a parse tree using fparser2
 - Follows the definition in the Fortran standard
- More detailed training as notebook, Follow tutorial link on <https://github.com/stfc/PSyclone/>
- Not necessary to fully understand fparser2 to use PSyclone
 - But fparser error messages might be thrown
 - Certain tools are best implemented on this level

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Example fparser Output

```

> from fparser.common.readfortran import FortranStringReader
> Code = "...a(i,j,k) = b(i,j,k) + 5*nj..."
> reader = FortranStringReader(code)
> from fparser.two.parser import ParserFactory
> parser = ParserFactory().create(std="f2003")
> parse_tree = parser(reader)

> print(str(parse_tree))
a(i,j,k) = b(i,j,k) + 5*nj
>
print(repr(parse_tree))
Assignment Stmt(Part_Ref(Name('a'), Section_Subscript_List(',', (Name('i'), Name('j'),
Name('k')))), '=', Level_2_Expr(Part_Ref(Name('b'), Section_Subscript_List(',',
(Name('i'), Name('j'), Name('k')))), '+', Add_Operand(Int_Literal_Constant('5', None),
 '*', Name('nj')))),

```

WHEN YOU START
WORKING LAST MINUTE AFTER
PROCRASTINATING FOR DAYS

y

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Fortran Grammar and fparser2 Representation

<code>assignment-stmt</code>	<code>variable = expr</code>	Extended Backus-Naur Form
<code>level-1-expr</code>	<code>[defined-unary-op] primary</code>	
<code>mult-operand</code>	<code>level-1-expr [power-op mult-operand]</code>	
<code>add-operand</code>	<code>[add-operand mult-op] mult-operand</code>	
<code>level-2-expr</code>	<code>[[level-2-expr] add-op] add-operand</code>	
<code>power-op</code>	<code>**</code>	
<code>mult-op</code>	<code>* or /</code>	
<code>add-op</code>	<code>+ or -</code>	


```

a(i) = b(i) + 5*n
Assignment Stmt(
  Part_Ref(Name('a'), Section_Subscript_List(',', (Name('i')))),
  '=',
  Level_2_Expr(Part_Ref(Name('b'), Section_Subscript_List(',', (Name('i')))),
    '+',
    Add_Operand(Int_Literal_Constant('5', None), '*', Name('n'))),
)
    
```

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fparser2 API: Dependencies Between Files

```

# From fparser/example/create_dependencies.py

parser = ParserFactory().create(std="f2008")
for filename in all_files:
    # Error handling removed
    reader = FortranFileReader(filename)

    parse_tree = parser(reader)

    # Find all `use` statements and get the module names
    for node in walk(parse_tree, Use Stmt):
        use_name = str(node.items[2])
        # filename depends on module `use_name`
        ...
    
```

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Fparser2 Discussion

- Can represent all of Fortran
 - That is ... if we had no bugs, and the Fortran language is not being extended ☺
 - And sometimes compiler accept code that is not standard confirming ☹
- Can be extended
 - Just follow the Fortran standard, implementation is following the grammar
 - Though in practice the devil is in the detail, e.g. order of rules can be important
- Performance very important
 - Also rule ordering important
- fparser2 is slowest part of PSyclone
 - Order of magnitude slower than a C(++) based compiled parser
 - E.g. not useful for syntax highlighting
- Can be hard to work with the grammar-based tree representation

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How PSyclone Works

2. Internal Representation: PSyIR

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PSyIR

- **PSyclone Internal Representation**
- A language-independent representation of a program
- Output can be produced in different languages by different backends
 - Fortran fully supported
 - Output in C possible
 - Used e.g. to interface with Kokkos, a C++ HPC framework
 - OpenCL
 - Based on C backend
 - SIR/DAWN (DSL framework, which can create cuda, gridtools)
 - SymPy, a Python symbolic maths package
 - Allows us to take a Fortran expression, and modify it (or reason about it) in SymPy

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Creating PSyIR

- PSyIR can be created by various frontends:
 - Fortran:
 - Uses fparser2 to create abstract syntax tree
 - This tree is then converted to PSyIR by the Fortran frontend
 - SymPy
 - We can convert SymPy expressions to PSyIR
 - Allows us to take a mathematical expression, modify it using SymPy, and insert the modified code in the PSyIR
 - We have started to experiment with python
- Can be created using Python/PSyclone functions
 - Used to create the PSy-layer
(caveat: not all of LFRic is currently created using PSyIR @ WIP)

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Special PSyIR Features

- Not all language features are represented naturally
 - Fortran case/switch becomes a sequence of IF statements
- Input/output is not represented at all
- PSyIR has a special 'CodeBlock' type
 - Any code that cannot be represented is stored as string in a codeblock
 - That will make it impossible to create output in any other language of course
 - PSyclone cannot reason about code (e.g. what variables are read/written)
- Can store directives
- A PSyIR has nested symbol tables to store type information
 - The Fortran backend will rename symbols if required, since Fortran has no full support for nested scopes
 - Supports features to create symbols that will not clash with user-defined symbols

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PSyclone and PSyIR

- PSyIR can be created by a frontend (parser)
 - Used e.g. when reading an algorithm or kernel layer file
- PSyIR can be created from scratch using python functions
 - Used when creating the PSy-layer
- PSyclone supplies functions to modify a PSyIR
 - So called transformations
 - Any user can easily write their own transformations from scratch, and/or use existing transformations to create more powerful transformations
- PSyclone provides tools to analyse a PSyIR
 - Low-level: which variables are used where with what indices
 - High-level: dependency analysis, can this loop be parallelised

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- ### PSyIR Tree Representation
- The PSyIR is a tree
 - Each node has a parent and children
 - A list of statements is represented by a `Schedule`
 - E.g. a loop body is one child node that is a schedule
 - Children are typically the parameters of a language construct, e.g.:
 - Loop has four children:
 - start, end, step, body
 - Addition:
 - first and second operand
 - Assignment:
 - left- and right-hand-side
 - To see the textual tree representation: `print(psyir_node.view())`
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Looking at Psy-layer PSyIR

```
GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_internal_pts']
  StructureReference[name:'neighbours']
  StructureMember[name:'internal']
  Member[name:'ystart']
  StructureReference[name:'neighbours']
  StructureMember[name:'internal']
  Member[name:'ystop']
  Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
  Schedule[]
  0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_internal_pts']
    StructureReference[name:'neighbours']
    StructureMember[name:'internal']
    Member[name:'xstart']
    StructureReference[name:'neighbours']
    StructureMember[name:'internal']
    Member[name:'xstop']
    Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
    Schedule[]
    0: CodedKern count_neighbours_code(neighbours,current)
```

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PSyIR of an Expression

$ztra = -ztr*(zwx(ji,jj,jk) - zwx(ji,jj,jk+1))$ →

```
0: Assignment[]
  Reference[name:'ztra']
  UnaryOperation[operator:'MINUS']
  BinaryOperation[operator:'MUL']
  Reference[name:'ztr']
  BinaryOperation[operator:'SUB']
  ArrayReference[name:'zwx']
  Reference[name:'ji']
  Reference[name:'jj']
  Reference[name:'jk']
  ArrayReference[name:'zwx']
  Reference[name:'ji']
  Reference[name:'jj']
  BinaryOperation[operator:'ADD']
  Reference[name:'jk']
  Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
```


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Colourful Output of PSyR

If `termcap` is installed:

```

0: Loop[type='lat', field_space='None', it_space='None']
  Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
  Reference[name:'jpj']
  Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
  Schedule: []
  0: Loop[type='lon', field_space='None', it_space='None']
    Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
    Reference[name:'jpi']
    Literal[value:'1', Scalar<INTEGER, UNDEFINED>]
    Schedule: []
    0: Assignment[]
      ArrayReference[name:'umask']
      Reference[name:'ji']
      Reference[name:'jj']
      Reference[name:'jk']
      BinaryOperation[operator:'DIV']
      BinaryOperation[operator:'MUL']
      BinaryOperation[operator:'MUL']
        Reference[name:'ji']
        Reference[name:'jj']
        Reference[name:'jk']
      Reference[name:'r']
    1: Assignment[]
      ArrayReference[name:'mydomain']
      Reference[name:'ji']
      Reference[name:'jj']
  
```

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Accessing Parameters of a PSyIR Node

- Mapping of parameters of a node to children might change
 - For example, the loop variable is currently not a child ☹
- Most nodes provide implementation-independent access functions:
 - Assignment: `lhs, rhs`
 - `assign.lhs = assign.children[0]` # Plus some consistency checks
 - Loop: `start_expr, stop_expr, step_expr, loop_body`
 - If: `condition, if_body, else_body`

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7. Introduction to PSyclone Transformations

This section introduces PSyclone transformations, i.e. the concept with which PSyclone can modify and optimise code. As a start, the Module Inlining transformation is introduced, followed by a hands-on sessions. Then the more complicated loop fusion transformation is used to further optimise the code. A final hand-on session finishes this introduction.

7.1 Module Inline Transformation - Slides

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Code Transformation with PSyclone – High Level

- The `psyclone` command can take a script as parameter (`-s`)
- PSyclone will first create the PSy-layer
- Then it will pass the PSy-layer to the `trans(psy)` function in the script
 - This object contains information about all invokes
 - Even if they are in different subroutines in the same file, `trans(psy)` is only called once
- The script can modify the PSy-layer in place
- PSyclone will then create the actual code using a backend

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Information in psy Object

- `psy` contains invoke information in `psy.invokes`:
 - `invoke_list`, a list of Invoke instances, and
 - `invoke_map` (mapping of invoke names to invoke object)
 - Both data structure contain the same invoke instances
 - Each invoke objects contains:
 - A `Schedule` with all loops for the kernel calls
 - Information about the arguments for all kernels
 - Each argument is only provided once to the PSy-layer
 - Only schedule is part of PSyIR
- It also contains a PSyIR container (= Fortran Module)
- **UPDATE: since PSyclone 3.0:**
 You get a PSyIR FileContainer as argument (but it is backwards compatible, i.e. provides a `invokes` attribute)

```

module my_psy
contains
  subroutine invoke_1(...)
  do ...
    call kernel1(...)
  do
    call kernel2(...)
  end subroutine invoke_1
  subroutine invoke_2(...)
  end subroutine invoke_2
end module my_psy
    
```

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OLD STYLE: The PSy-layer Object in `apply (psy)` :

- `psy` contains invoke information in `psy.invokes`:
 - First is a list of invokes, second a mapping of invoke-names to invokes, both point to the same objects
 - Each `invoke=psy.invokes.invoke_list[n]`:
 - `invoke.schedule`: list of loops for all kernels (and other created code) in this invoke
 - The invoke is NOT part of the PSyIR, it's just a small convenience class that stores invoke information (e.g. list of unique arguments to all kernel calls in this invoke)

- Example loop structure for `trans (psy)`:

```
for invoke in psy.invokes.invoke_list:
    print("Invoke", invoke)
    schedule = invoke.schedule
    for kern in schedule.walk(GOKern):
        print("  Kern", kern)
```

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New Style: FileContainer as `psyir`

```
for sched in psyir.walk(InvokeSchedule):
    print("invoke", sched.name)
    for kern in sched.walk(GOKern):
        print("  kern", kern.name)
```

Or a single kernel:

```
schedule = psyir.walk(InvokeSchedule)[0]
```

Or:

```
for subroutine in psyir.walk(Routine):
    if subroutine.name == "invoke_initialise_fields":
        for child in subroutine.children:
            if isinstance(child, Loop): ...
```

Kernels:

```
for kern in psyir.kernels():
```

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Sample Output

- One invoke with four kernels:

```
invoke_compute(neighbours, current, born, die)
kern call: count_neighbours_code
kern call: compute_born_code
kern call: compute_die_code
kern call: combine_code
```
- Two invokes, each with two kernels

```
invoke_0(neighbours, current, born)
kern call: count_neighbours_code
kern call: compute_born_code
invoke_compute(die, current, neighbours, born)
kern call: compute_die_code
kern call: combine_code
```


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Existing Transformations

- PSyclone provides a long list of transformations
- They need to be called from a user-defined script
 - E.g. these standard transformations cannot be used on the command line
- Two phases:
 - `validate()`: make sure that the transformation to be applied does not create invalid code
 - No actual code change, will raise `TransformationError()`
 - `apply()`: call `validate()`, then apply the actual transformations
- The `validate()` function can be used in 'higher level' scripts
 - E.g. check if a sequence of kernels can all be parallelised, then combine them into one parallel region

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Module Inlining

- Some compilers (esp. gfortran) cannot inline code that is in a different file.
 - Apply 'module inlining' (to be renamed to something else ☺), which means to copy the subroutine into the PSy-layer module
 - No actual change to the tree, this just sets a flag in the kernels, which will change if the kernel is 'used' (not inlined), or copied into the same program unit ('module inline'), in which case it will be found without import.

```
from psychone.domain.common.transformations import \
    KernelModuleInlineTrans

def trans(psy):
    inline = KernelModuleInlineTrans()
    # For each kernel ... loops skipped here
    inline.apply(kern)
```

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Hands-on 2.6: Module Inlining

- Look at directory 2.6-GameOfLife-fuse (no typo, fuse will come next ☺)
- Note that most source code is now taken from the shared ../gol directory
 - Only the actual algorithm layer file `time_step_alg_mod.x90` is in each directory
- Modify the `inline.py` script first to print the PSyIR of each invoke
 - Note that the invoke is not part of the PSyIR, you need to do:


```
print(schedule.view())
```
 - Verify by changing the invoke structure in `time_step_mod.x90`
- Modify the `inline.py` script to create an instance of the module inline transformation (once)
- Apply inlining to each kernel (see loop structure three slides earlier)
- Check the created `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90` file

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7.2 Module Inline Transformation - Hands on

Directory: PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.6-GameOfLife-fuse

The measurement at the end of the previous training module showed that there can be a significant performance loss with the initial version of the PSyclone Game of Life. In this module we will apply some transformations to improve the performance of the code.

7.2.1 Inlining

As is obvious from the code being able to inline the kernel calls is essential for good performance. If a call needs to be executed for the computations for each cell, the compiler cannot use vectorisation, and the call overhead itself is likely higher than the time required for the actual computations.

The Intel compiler is able (given the right compiler options) to inline code that is contained in a different program unit. It is able to inline the kernels contained in the various kernel files into the psy-layer file, and can then vectorise the loop.

The GNU Fortran compiler on the other hand is not able to inline code from a different file, but it can inline successfully if the code is contained in the same file.

At this stage PSyclone does not yet have full inlining capabilities (as in putting the whole kernel code inside the nested loops in the psy-layer). But it can move the code from the kernel files into the psy-layer files, which in turn will enable GNU Fortran to inline the kernel calls.

In order to do this, the PSyclone inline transformation has to be applied to each kernel that should be inlined. This requires a script which PSyclone will call after the psy-layer has been created, but before the Fortran code is produced.

The following example script shows a script that will inline the first kernel. It imports the inline transformation `KernelModuleInlineTrans` to be used on the kernels that should be inlined. It then gets the psy-layer representation of the `invoke_compute` `invoke` statement. Have a look at `time_step_alg_mod.x90` to see the name 'compute' used in the one `invoke` statement. It then takes the first kernel in this schedule (`schedule[0]`) and applies the inline transformation.

```
from psyclone.transformations import \
    KernelModuleInlineTrans
from psyclone.gocean1p0 import GOKern

def trans(psyir):
    '''
    Take the supplied psyir object, and apply module
    inlining.

    :param psy: the PSy layer to transform.
    :type psy: :py:class:`psyclone.psyGen.PSy`

    :returns: the transformed PSy object.
    :rtype: :py:class:`psyclone.psyGen.PSy`

    '''
    inline = KernelModuleInlineTrans()
```

```

for subroutine in psyir.kernels:
    if subroutine.name == "invoke_compute":
        inline.apply(subroutine)

```

If you now invoke PSyclone with the additional parameter `-s inline.py`, the script will be invoked by PSyclone, and inlining for the first kernel will be enabled.

Look at the psy-layer output file. While the nested loops and kernel call inside these loops have not changed, the difference is that the kernel called is now contained in the same file. This will help the compilers, especially the GNU Fortran compiler, with inlining, which can make a significant performance difference.

7.2.2 Measure the performance.

Obviously, just inlining one kernel is not enough, all kernels should be inlined. Modify the inline script to find all invokes and all kernels in each invoke, and apply the inline transformation to them. As shown in the presentation, you can use `psy.invokes.invoke_list` to get a list of all invoke objects, and then use `invoke.schedule.walk(GOKern)` to get an iterator over all kernels in a schedule.

What is performance with the GNU Fortran compiler after inlining all kernels?

7.3 Loop Fusion Transformation - Slides

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Loop Fusion Transformation

- Using many small kernels might be good for testing and software design
- Bad for performance ☹
 - Loop overhead (e.g. increasing loop counter, comparing it)
 - Data will likely be out of first level cache
- We use PSyclone to fuse (combine) loops
 - Of course, often a compiler can do this
 - But we have total control this way
 - And we can be sure it works on all compilers

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Loop Fusion in Game of Life

```
do j
  do i
    call count_neighbours(i, j, neighbours, current)
  enddo
enddo
do j
  do i
    call compute_born(i, j, born, current, neighbours)
  enddo
enddo
→
do j
  do i
    call count_neighbours(i, j, neighbours, current)
    call compute_born(i, j, born, current, neighbours)
  enddo
enddo
```

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Loop Fusion Transformation

- The existing transformation can fuse two consecutive loops
 - The validate function will check that the loop indices are identical
 - TODO: make sure that the fused code is still correct (dependency analysis)
 - ATM too conservative, i.e. it will reject code that could be fused – work-in-progress
- This transformation has different implementation for different domains
 - E.g. LFRic implementation will check for same function space instead of just loop boundaries, handle reductions when the result of a reduction in the first loop is used in the second (side note: GOcean does not yet support reductions)

```
from psyclone.domain.gocean.transformations import \
    GOceanLoopFuseTrans
```

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Loop Fusion Step by Step

```
Schedule
[0] Do j
      [0] do i
            call count_neighbours_code
[1] Do j
      [0] do i
            call compute_born_code
[2] Do j
      [0] do i
            call compute_die_code
[3] Do j
      [0] do i
            call combine_code

gocean_fuse.apply(schedule[0], schedule[1])
```

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Fuse First Outer Loops (1)

```
Schedule
[0]   Do j
      [0]   do i
            call count_neighbours_code
      [1]   do i
            call compute_born_code
[1]   Do j
      [0]   do i
            call compute_die_code
[2]   Do j
      [0]   do i
            call combine_code

gocean_fuse.apply(schedule[0], schedule[1])
```

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Fuse Next Outer Loops (2)

```
Schedule
[0]   Do j
      [0]   do i
            call count_neighbours_code
      [1]   do i
            call compute_born_code
      [2]   do i
            call compute_die_code
[1]   Do j
      [0]   do i
            call combine_code

Can we do it one more time?
```

d

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Fuse Next Outer Loops (2)

```

[0]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call count_neighbours_code
      [1]  do i
            call compute_born_code
      [2]  do i
            call compute_die_code
      [3]  do i
            call combine_code
  
```


- Assume the **yellow** rows are done
- When doing the **red** line, `count_neighbours()` reads the status of all eight neighbours
 - This includes already **updated** and white rows, which are not yet updated!
- This is not a PSyclone restriction, the data flow does not allow to combine the loops

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Loop Fusion and Dependency Analysis ☹️

- The `validate()` function should trigger an error in this case
 - Ticket #257/1075. We have made some good progress with the dependency analysis (e.g. adding SymPy), but have focussed on parallelisation related issues first
- A different solution would be to fuse the last three loops, that would be valid as well
 - The problem is reading in the stencil access values that are updated in the `combine` function.
 - The other loops are just reading point-wise (no stencil), they are fine either way
- Or the new status could be written to a new field
 - Which then later becomes the current field ... though that's not very efficient

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Fuse First Inner Loops

```
Schedule
[0]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call count_neighbours_code
      [1]  do i
            call compute_born_code
      [2]  do i
            call compute_die_code
[1]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call combine_code

gocean_fuse.apply(schedule[0].loop_body[0], schedule[0].loop_body[1])
```

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Fuse First Inner Loops (2)

```
Schedule
[0]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call count_neighbours_code
            call compute_born_code
      [1]  do i
            call compute_die_code
[1]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call combine_code

gocean_fuse(schedule[0].loop_body[0], schedule[0].loop_body[1])
```

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Fuse First Inner Loops (2)

```

Schedule
[0]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call count_neighbours_code
            call compute_born_code
            call compute_die_code
[1]  Do j
      [0]  do i
            call combine_code

DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart, neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart, neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
  CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data, current%data)
  CALL compute_born_code(i, j, born%data, current%data, neighbours%data)
  CALL compute_die_code(i, j, die%data, current%data, neighbours%data)
END DO
END DO

```

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Hands-on 2.6

- Directory 2.6-GameOfLife-fuse
- Modify the makefile to use `fuse_loops.py` instead of `inline.py` (twice)
 - `Make clean`
- Finish the `fuse_loops.py` script by fusing the first three outer and inner loops
 - You can use `print(schedule.view())` to see the tree changing
- Fuse the last three outer and inner loops instead
- You can try to use the larger glider configuration to measure performance
 - It's not what I would have expected ☹

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Hands-on 2.6

- Fuse all four loops
 - This should fail when running PSyclone with a useless error message ... work-in-progress
- You can disable the dependency check by using:

```
fuse.apply(schedule[0], schedule[1], options={'force': True})
```

 - Details about options will come a bit later
 - This is an override to allow the user to make decisions, e.g. because an expert might know more
 - Example: indirect access `a(ind(i))`
user might know that `ind` does not contain duplicated elements
 - Run the check (make test), which should now fail
- With great power comes great responsibility

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7.4 Loop Fusion - Hands on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.6-GameOfLife-fuse](#)

7.4.1 Loop Fusion of Outer Loops

The original design of splitting the code into several small kernels is typically not ideal from a performance point of view, since hardly any data is being reused and data needs to be loaded from memory, instead from cache. But from a software engineering point of view splitting the code into smaller kernels offer better testing opportunities: in the Game of Life example you can independently test counting the neighbours, determining dying and newly born cells, and combining the results. In case of test failures less manual work is required to find the reason. With PSyclone it is possible to design your code in smaller kernels, but then use transformation scripts to optimise the code to give better performance.

At the moment, the code created looks like this:

```
do j
  do i
    call count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  enddo
enddo
do j
  do i
    call compute_born(born,current, neighbours)
```

Counting the neighbours will mean that the values of `current` and `neighbours` will be in cache, but (for larger fields) the cache will not be big enough to store the whole arrays, and by the time `compute_born` is executed, the data needs to be reloaded from memory. The performance could be improved by combining the loops:

```
do j
  do i
    call count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  enddo
  do i
    call compute_born(born,current, neighbours)
```

or even:

```
do j
  do i
    call count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
    call compute_born(born,current, neighbours)
```

Which one is better might depend on the actual code used, size of the fields, compiler optimisations applied, etc. The first version will have to store one row of `neighbours` and `current` in cache in order to improve performance, while the second version will immediately reuse individual values (and will have slightly less loop overhead).

Note that for training purpose we individually apply the loop fusion in this training material. For a real application you would have one script that would apply all required inlining automatically.

The first version can be created by using the `LoopFuse` transformation once. Looking at the

schedule, the original loops look like this (several lines of additional details have been removed):

```
GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
  0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct',
         it_space='go_internal_pts']
    Schedule[]
      0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct',
             it_space='go_internal_pts']
        Schedule[]
          0: CodedKern count_neighbours_
code(neighbours,current) [module_inline=True]
      1: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct',
             it_space='go_internal_pts']
        Schedule[]
          0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct',
                 it_space='go_internal_pts']
            Schedule[]
              0: CodedKern compute_born_code(born,
current,neighbours)
                [module_inline=True]
```

The outer schedule (GOInvokeSchedule) has two children for the first two loops. So you need to provide these two children to the fuse transformation to combine the loops:

```
fuse = GOceanLoopFuseTrans()

invoke = psy.invokes.get("invoke_compute")
schedule = invoke.schedule

# To see the schedule before it is transformed:
# print(schedule.view())

# Now merge the first two loops
fuse.apply(schedule[0], schedule[1])

# print(schedule.view())
```

This results in the following schedule:

```
0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_
internal_pts']
  Schedule[]
    0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
      Schedule[]
        0: CodedKern count_neighbours_
code(neighbours,current) [module_inline=True]
      1: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
        Schedule[]
          0: CodedKern compute_born_code(born,
current,neighbours) [module_inline=True]
```

The resulting Fortran code looks like this:

```

DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,
neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
  DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
    CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
current%data)
  END DO
  DO i = born%internal%xstart, born%internal%xstop, 1
    CALL compute_born_code(i, j, born%data, current%data,
neighbours%data)
  END DO
END DO

```

Extend this script to merge the first three outer loops together, and measure the performance. Notice that the provided script `fuse_loops.py` already contains code to enable inlining of each kernel.

Note that PSyclone will check the iteration spaces of the loops to be merged, i.e. that the loop boundaries are identical among the fused loops.

7.4.2 Loop Fusion of Inner Loops

The performance can be improved further by next inlining all the inner loops as well. Looking at the fused schedule reveals:

```

GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
  0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_
internal_pts']
    Schedule[]
      0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
        Schedule[]
          0: CodedKern count_neighbours_
code(neighbours,current) [module_inline=True]
            1: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
              Schedule[]
                0: CodedKern compute_born_code(born,
current,neighbours) [module_inline=True]

```

In order to fuse the inner loops, you need to access the schedule of the outer loop. This schedule can be accessed using the `loop_body` attribute, e.g.:

```

fuse.apply(schedule[0].loop_body[0],
           schedule[0].loop_body[1])

```

Adding this loop fusion to the script will generate the following output (again shortened):

```

0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_
internal_pts']
  Schedule[]
    0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
      Schedule[]

```

```
0: CodedKern count_neighbours_
code(neighbours,current) [module_inline=True]
1: CodedKern compute_born_code(born,
current,neighbours) [module_inline=True]
```

and the corresponding Fortran code:

```
DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,
neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
  DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
    CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
current%data)
    CALL compute_born_code(i, j, born%data, current%data,
neighbours%data)
  END DO
END DO
```

Now extend this script to completely fuse all three nested loops.

7.4.3 Why are not All Four Loops Fused?

If you look at the first and last loop, you will notice that the last loop writes the field `current`, and the first loop has a stencil access to `current`. This means the code would be incorrect if all four loops are fused. The first loop would read `current(i-1, j)` and `current(i+1, j)` - the first of which would have the updated value written in the previous loop iteration in the fourth loop, but the latter one has not been updated.

Note that at the moment PSyclone does detect that loop fusion would create incorrect code, but this test is too conservative, i.e. it will reject code that could be fused. This is work in progress. Also, the error message is by far not detailed enough.

7.4.4 Optional Fusing Task 1

Instead of fusing the first three loops, it is also possible to fuse the last three loops. Modify the `loop_fuse` script to fuse the last three loops, and measure the performance.

8. Parallelisation with PSyclone

This next section shows how PSyclone can be used to parallelise code. It covers both shared memory parallelisation using OpenMP, and distributed memory parallelisation using MPI. The latter will introduce the concept of halo (or ghost) regions. It is worth noting that PSyclone itself is not restricted to use MPI for distributed memory parallelisation. It is using functions in the infrastructure library `dl_esm_inf`, which are implemented using MPI.

Each of the two sections is followed by a hands-on task. This will also show how previous transformations, like loop fusion and module inlining, can be combined with parallelisation.

8.1 OpenMP Parallelisation - Slides

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Simple OpenMP

- Just apply `parallel do` around outer loops:

```
from psyclone.transformations import OMPParallelLoopTrans

omp_parallel = OMPParallelLoopTrans(omp_schedule="dynamic")
omp_parallel.omp_schedule = "static"
omp_parallel.apply(loop_node)
```

- GOcean loops have an attribute `loop_type` which is "inner" or "outer"
- Loop over all loops, if `loop.loop_type` is "outer", apply transformation
 - Use `walk` (as previously) for type `GOLoop` (already imported in example)
- Not very efficient (due to repeatedly starting threads for each loop), but extremely simple to apply.

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More Efficient Approach

- Apply `omp do` to each loop, and surround with `omp parallel`.

```
from psyclone.transformations import OMPLoopTrans, OMPParallelTrans

omp_parallel = OMPParallelTrans()
omp_do = OMPLoopTrans(omp_schedule="static") # optional parameter
omp_do.schedule = "static" # or dynamic etc
```

- You apply `omp_do` for all outer loop
- Then apply `omp_parallel` to the schedule (`invoke.schedule`)
- Can obviously be combined with loop fusion
 - If done correctly, you can call existing fusion script
 - 'correctly' meaning: e.g. don't keep pointer to loop, since e.g. loop fuse will modify the tree (delete loops)

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Task Parallelism

- PSyclone also recently started to support task parallelism
- A more flexible approach to the previous `OMP` section
- We won't cover this here
 - The example isn't really suited ☺
- Just remember that it does exist
- And it works pretty similar to the existing OpenMP transformations

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Hands-On 2.8

1. Finish the `openmp.py` script to add `parallel do` across any outer loop
2. Finish the `openmp_combined.py` script to add separate `omp do` and `omp parallel`
3. Apply loop fuse as well.
 1. You can reuse the existing loop fuse trans script
4. To see how good PSyclone can get:
 1. Modify `fuse_loops.py` to merge all four loops by adding the `force` option (i.e. we force to create kind of incorrect code)
 2. Assuming that the combined code is what the user wants, try to parallelise it
 3. You will get a hopefully helpful error message indicating why this is incorrect
 - You could supply the `force` option again to overwrite, but then the results will be really wrong

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8.2 OpenMP Parallelisation - Hands-on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.8-GameOfLife-openmp/](#)

PSyclone offers the ability to apply OpenMP parallelisation to your code using transformations. It therefore requires you to write a script to actually apply the transformations, but you can create a very general script that will be able to be used for different code bases. In this exercise though we will focus on a custom script for the parallelisation of Game of Life.

8.2.1 Simple Parallel Version

As a first start we use a script to add a `omp parallel do` directive. The transformation script follows the script for loop fusion:

```
from psyclone.transformations import OMPParallelLoopTrans
omp_parallel = OMPParallelLoopTrans()

invoke = psy.invokes.get("invoke_compute")
schedule = invoke.schedule

omp_parallel.apply(schedule[0])
```

You can see the inserted OMP parallel directive in the schedule:

```
GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
0: OMPParallelDoDirective[]
  Schedule[]
    0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
      Schedule[]
...

```

This will generate the following Fortran code:

```
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(i,j),
schedule(static)
DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,
neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
  DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
    CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
current%data)
  END DO
END DO
!$omp end parallel do
```

Todo:

Now extend the script to apply parallel loop directive to all kernels.

You can run the parallel version using:

```
OMP_NUM_THREADS=4 ./gol ../gol-lib/config.glider-large
```

8.2.2 A More General Script to Apply Loop Parallelisation

Each loop object in the GOcean API has a `loop_type`, which is either `inner` or `outer`. Using this, the script can be simplified by using a walk over all `GOLoops`, and applying the OMP loop parallelisation to any loop that is an outer loop. Rewrite the script to use this approach.

8.2.3 Using Parallel Do for Better Performance

The performance of the parallel code is not very good. The reason for this is that there is a runtime cost associated with starting the threads, and each OMP parallel do statement will first create the threads, and then destroy them. And with the kernels being very small, there just is too much overhead to make the parallelisation efficient.

This can be improved by using separate OMP do statement for each loop, and only one OMP parallel which spans all loops to be parallelised. PSyclone offers the separate transformation to apply the OMP parallel and OMP do. The `OMPParallelTrans` also accepts a list of nodes. It doesn't matter in which order you apply the transformations, but applying the `OMPParallelTrans` will change the tree - it inserts a `OMPParallel` node at the top of the schedule, so if you want to access the loops, they are now children of this `OMPParallelNode`:

```
omp_parallel = OMPParallelTrans()
omp_do = OMPLoopTrans()
omp_parallel.apply(schedule[0:2]) # Apply to loops 0 and 1
```

Which results in:

```
GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
  0: OMPParallelDirective[]
    Schedule[]
      0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
      1: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_
space='go_internal_pts']
      1: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space='go_
internal_pts']
```

You can see that accessing the first two loops, which are now surrounded by an OMP Parallel, are deeper in the tree. So it might be easier to first apply the `OMPLoopTrans`, which adds an OMP do node around each outer loop, and then applying the outer OMP parallel.

Todo

Use the `OMPParallelTrans` and `OMPLoopTrans` transformations to optimise the parallelisation of the first three loops by adding a single outer OMP parallel section, followed by individual OMP do directives for each outer loop.

8.2.4 Using Dynamic Schedule

The constructor for any OMP loop takes an optional argument that specifies the schedule to be used. It defaults to a static schedule. There are two ways to create a different schedule. First you can specify the schedule when creating the instance of the loop transformation:

```
omp_do_dynamic = OMPLoopTrans(omp_schedule="dynamic")
```

By using this instance when applying the OMP loop transformation, a `schedule(dynamic)` will be created. Alternatively, you can also assign the schedule to the `omp_schedule` attribute:

```
omp_do.omp_schedule = "dynamic"
```

Valid options for the schedule are: `runtime`, `static`, `dynamic`, `guided`, and `auto`.

Todo

Use a different schedule in your parallelisation script.

8.2.5 More Optimisations - Combine Loop Fusion and OpenMP

Obviously, we can expect an even better performance if we have less loop, with kernels that do more work (since there is less loop- and thread-synchronisation overhead). So we want to combine the loop fusion code from the previous loop fusion exercise with the OpenMP parallelisation code.

You could either copy the loop fusion code into `openmp.py`, or you could import the transformation, and apply it. Importing it has the advantage that you have less duplicated code. But on the other hand you risk that changes to `fuse_loops.py` might affect your `openmp.py` script unexpectedly - while in many cases that is good (e.g. improvements to `fuse_loops.py` will flow into other scripts), but they could also break your `openmp.py` script unexpectedly. In a later session we will address the issue of writing 'intelligent' scripts.

The important part of importing is to make sure to rename the the transformation when importing, since otherwise all transformation scripts will have the function `trans`, and one would overwrite the other, resulting in `trans` recursively calling itself:

```
from fuse_loops import trans as fuse_trans
```

Then you can just call `fuse_trans(psyir)` in your parallelisation script. Be aware that after applying the full fusion of the loops, there will be only one loop left to be put into an OMP parallel region (in which case there is no advantage of using two separate transformations, a single one to apply `OMP parallel do` will be sufficient).

8.3 Distributed Memory Parallelisation

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Distributed Memory

- How do you parallelise a grid-based application if you can't use shared memory?
- Each process computes its part of the grid:

- Works for computing cells that die, are born, and to combine

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Stencil (Neighbour) Accesses?

- To count the neighbours, you need to have information from other processes
- Add halo (or ghost) rows/columns (as done previously)

- Halos can be larger than one row/column
 - Depends on the operation required

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Stencil Accesses?

- Each process needs data from the neighbour in its halo regions
- Halo exchange

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Stencil Accesses?

- Each process needs data from the neighbour in its halo regions
- Halo exchange

- Restrictions of kernels: they are only allowed to write to `field(i, j)`
 - This guarantees that a process is not writing into the halo region

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Implementation of Distributed Memory in dl_esm_inf

- When constructing a grid in dl_esm_inf, we can specify a domain decomposition
 - I.e. how many processes in x and y direction:


```
grid%go_decompose(domainx, domainy, &
                  ndomains, ndomainx, ndomainy, &
                  halo_width)
```
 - Parameters ndomains, ndomainx, ndomainy are **optional**
 - By default, will be taken from number of processes, with a 'suarish' domain decomposition
 - dl_esm_inf needs to be configured with MPI support
- When outputting results, we need to combine all local domain data on the root process:


```
real(go_wp), dimension(:,:), allocatable :: global_dat
call field%gather_inner_data(global_data)
```
- This is all done in the files in ../gol-lib

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Implementation of Halo Exchanges

- Halo exchanges can be implemented in many different ways
 - MPI obviously
 - Shared memory (if running within one node)
 - Distributed shared memory ('write into memory of other process')
 - Also possible with MPI – one-sided communication
- In GOcean, we get support for halo exchanges from the infrastructure library
 - Just do:


```
call field%halo_exchange(1)
```
 - Parameter is the number of halo rows/columns
 - Can be less than the actual halo size specified in the grid

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How to Implement Distributed Memory with PSyclone

- Set up domain decomposition when creating the grid
- Take care of initialising fields
 - Needs to be done by application
 - Very unoptimised convenience functionality:

```
initial = r2d_field(grid, grid_points = GO_T_POINTS, &
                  init_global_data = initial_state)
```

 - In general, it is stupid to read the whole input file on all processes, just to initialise their local domain
- Add the command line option `-dm` to the PSyclone command
 - Yes, that's all

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Automatic Halo Exchanges

- PSyclone will insert halo exchanges
- If a field is accessed using a stencil
 - This indicates that we need halo information
 - Execute a halo exchange before calling the kernel
 - Depth of halo exchange is taken from stencil information in meta-data

When you're a programmer and see a hacking scene in a movie

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2-10 Hands-on

- The example Game of Life code already has the initialisation of fields from the global start configuration, no change required.
- There are two different version of `dl_esm_info`, configured either to use no MPI, or support MPI
 - First time the MPI version of `dl_esm_inf` will be compiled automatically by the Makefile
- The only required change is to add `-dm` to the PSyclone command line
 - No script is required
- Check the PSy-layer file for halo exchange calls

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2-10 Hands-on

- The Makefile contains `'MPI=no'` (which results in using `-nodm` flag)
 - Change this to be yes, and do a `'make'`.
 - No script is required or used
- Check the PSyclone command line to make sure it has `'-dm'`
- Look at the created psy-layer file `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90`
 - Where is the halo exchange?

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Hands-on 2.10

- The existing scripts we have can all be combined with distributed memory:
- Supply the `fuse_loop.py` script as parameter
 - This is a modified version, which will print out the schedule first
 - What difference is between this schedule and the one in hands-on 2.6
 - Hint: look at the first node in the printed schedule
 - How else was this script modified in order to work?
 - Note that there will be a section later about 'smart scripting' ☺
- You can try to combine distributed memory with OpenMP (and fuse and inlining as well)
 - The simple OpenMP script will work without any change (why?)
- Try to use `openmp_combined.py`
 - You get an error. Fix the script ☺

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8.4 Distributed Memory Parallelisation - Hands-on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.10-GameOfLife-mpi](#)

In this session we will add support for distributed memory parallelisation using MPI. Adding MPI support does not require any transformation to be applied, MPI support is added by a combination of infrastructure functionality, here `dl_esm_inf`, and the way PSyclone creates the PSy-layer.

Consequently, this session does not involve a lot of coding, since most of the work is done automatically by PSyclone

MPI Support in the Infrastructure Library

The infrastructure library provides the following functionality to support distributed memory parallelisation.

1. Parallel Initialisation

The infrastructure can be compiled with MPI support. This library is then called `lib_dm_fd.a` (instead of `lib_df.a`). The API for the user application is identical, but it will use MPI at initialisation time. The distributed memory version of this library will recognise if it was started with more than one process, and in this case compute a suitable domain decomposition for the given number of processes. It will also add a halo region for each field, which is used to store the field values from neighbouring processes. It is possible for the user to overwrite these defaults (e.g. by manually specifying the domain decomposition), but in this example we will keep the defaults, which will result in a domain decomposition to be as close to a square as possible. Similarly, when finalising, it will internally call `MPI_Finalize()`.

2. Distributing Data

When creating a field and providing it with a pointer to initial data, only the locally required data is copied into the field. This is not very efficient for large application (since each process needs to read in the global field), but given the very simple and short input file size this is acceptable for this application.

3. Gathering Local Data

The field object provides a method to gather the local data from all processes into a 2d array on the master. This is used for the simple output functionality.

4. Halo Exchanges

The field object also provides a function for a halo exchange.

The first three items mean that there is no change required in startup, distributing the input data and printing the output data. All these calls will transparently work with MPI, if the distributed memory version `lib_dm_fd` is linked in.

8.4.1 Adding Halo Exchanges

The only required change is adding halo exchanges, since counting the number of neighbours means that updated information from neighbouring processes is required. And luckily, this error-prone step can be done automatically by PSyclone.

PSyclone relies on the meta-data provided for each kernel. Especially in `count_`

`neighbours_mod` the declaration is:

```

type(go_arg), dimension(2) :: meta_args =      &
  (/go_arg(GO_WRITE, GO_CT, GO_POINTWISE),    &
   go_arg(GO_READ, GO_CT, GO_STENCIL(111,    &
                                             101, &
                                             111)) &
  /)

```

This indicates that the second argument, the current information about empty and filled cells, is accessed using a stencil-operation of depth 1. The infrastructure library will do the required halo exchange, acquiring the current data from all eight neighbours. And PSyclone will automatically insert calls to halo-exchanges for any required field.

To add MPI support, use the PSyclone command line flag `-dm` (for distributed memory):

```

psyclone -l output -dm -d ../gol-lib -api gocean
         -oalg time_step_alg_mod.f90
         -opsy time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90
         time_step_alg_mod.x90

```

Inspecting the PSy-layer output file `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90` shows:

```

SUBROUTINE invoke_0_count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  USE count_neighbours_mod, ONLY: count_neighbours_code
  ...
  CALL current%halo_exchange(1)
  DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,
       neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
    DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
         neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
      CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
                                current%data)
    END DO
  END DO
END SUBROUTINE invoke_0_count_neighbours

```

You see that immediately before the kernel that counts the neighbours the halo exchange is automatically triggered. Note that at this stage the infrastructure library (and therefore also PSyclone) only supports halo exchanges of depth 1.

8.4.2 Combination with other Transformations

MPI can obviously work together with other transformations. Provide the `fuse_loops.py` script as parameter, and check the created output file or the displayed schedule.

You can also combine distributed memory with OpenMP. Start with using the script `openmp.py` from example 2.8 (a copy is in this directory). This results in the following PSy-layer:

```

CALL current%halo_exchange(1)
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(i,j),
schedule(static)
DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart,

```

```

neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
    DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart,
neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
        CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data,
current%data)
    END DO
END DO
!$omp end parallel do
!$omp parallel do default(shared), private(i,j),
schedule(static)
    DO j = born%internal%ystart, born%internal%ystop, 1
        DO i = born%internal%xstart, born%internal%xstop, 1
            CALL compute_born_code(i, j, born%data, current%data,
neighbours%data)
        ...

```

Each kernel is included in an openmp parallel do, so the loops over rows are parallelised using OpenMP.

Todo

Then try to use the `openmp_combined.py` script from the previous example (a copy is in this directory). It doesn't work. Why do you get an error?

Fix the script.

The reason for the error is the modified tree structure due to the added halo exchange. Fix the `openmp_combined.py` script to work here. Notice that later we will address more intelligent scripting.

9. Psyclone Instrumentation Interface PSyData

Psyclone provides an API that allows external and third-party libraries to be linked in. A transformation can be applied that will provide information to these libraries, for example the name of a kernel that is executed next, and when a kernel execution has finished. Psyclone can also provide access to variables used (directly or indirectly) in the kernel execution.

Example applications of the PSyData API are listed on the slides. The hands-on session will introduce the usage of PsyData for profiling, value range check, and kernel extraction.

9.1 PSyclone Instrumentation Interface - Slides

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PSyclone Instrumentation Interface - PSyData

- PSyData is an instrumentation interface that allows third party libraries to be written that are called and can access data before and/or after a kernel call.
- A full usage requires two parts:
 - Transformation that (automatically) inserts the required calls into the PSy-layer
 - A Fortran library that implements additional functionality
 - Has been used to call Python functions – Fortran → C → Python!
 - In some cases, the Fortran library relies on other third-party libraries, e.g. profiling
- Requires to link in (or compile) additional libraries into the application!

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Existing Application of PSyData (1)

- Profiling
 - No data is actually provided, but a call before and after a kernel is added
- Verify variable value ranges
 - User can specify environment variable to define minimum and/or maximum value of variables
 - Will additionally check for NaNs or infinity
 - Check of input variables before kernel, and output variables after kernel.
 - *(PR submitted, but not yet available on trunk)*
- Readonly verification
 - Compute a checksum for readonly variables before and after a kernel call
 - Obviously, compiler will detect write to a `intent(in)` variable, but memory overwrite can happen.

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Existing Application of PSyData (2)

- Kernel extraction
 - Write all input- and output-data to a file
 - Create a driver program that reads the file, executes the kernel, and compares the result
 - GOcean implementation needs some catchup with recent LFRic work, e.g. no MPI support
 - Has the ability to collect non-local variable access
 - E.g. a kernel calls `sub1` which calls `sub2`, which uses some pre-computed or initialised variable
 - The driver will contain all required modules, i.e. it is a single (long) program
 - Can be over 10k lines
 - Restrictions: procedure pointers, overwritten method
 - Generic interfaces work by visiting all possible functions
- Works with all of gungho (and gravity wave ...)
 - LFRic_atm has some issues with some UM code (not finding sources of a module, and some coding constructs that are not used in LFRic kernels ... work-in-progress)

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Future Applications of PSyData

- Support for ML
 - Training – take the data directly from model runs
 - ML testing – before a kernel do the ML based computation
 - After kernel: compare the results
- In-situ visualisation
 - See graphs of fields while the simulation is running (prototype exists)
- Access tracing:
 - E.g. a crash somewhere is caused by invalid data in a field. Where was a field written previously?
 - Trace all input and output fields → we can check where a field was written before
 - More interesting: Can we automatically trace back 'bad' values?
 - Combined with variable value range checking?

WHEN YOU CAN'T FIND ANSWERS ON STACKOVERFLOW

A

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Using Transformation to Insert Calls

- The PSyData transformation adds calls in three phases
 - Inspired by NetCDF: first declare variables, then provide the data before
- First declare all variables that will be provided
 - Can be 0 variables
 - Some libraries ignore this phase by implementing empty subroutines
- Then provide data before the call
- Lastly, provide data after the call
- Which variables these are is up to the transformation, e.g.:
 - None (profiling)
 - All input variable to a kernel before the call, and all output after (range checking)

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Full Example

Number of variables before and after kernel

Module and subroutine name (together unique name)

```

CALL extract_psy_data%PreStart("update_field_mod", "update_field_code", &
1, 1)
CALL extract_psy_data%PreDeclareVariable("a_fld", a_fld)
CALL extract_psy_data%PreDeclareVariable("b_fld", b_fld)
CALL extract_psy_data%PreEndDeclaration
CALL extract_psy_data%ProvideVariable("a_fld", a_fld)
CALL extract_psy_data%PreEnd
! Loop to call kernel b(:) = a(:)
CALL extract_psy_data%PostStart
CALL extract_psy_data%ProvideVariable("b_fld", b_fld)
CALL extract_psy_data%PostEnd
    
```

'Declare' call, specifying name of each variable and its value

'Provide' call, same parameter as declare

'Provide' call after the kernel, same parameter as declare

- Declare&provide inspired by NetCDF
- If required (to distinguish provide calls before and after) keep state information

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Detailed Look at PSyData API

- Implementation uses inheritance and generic interface:


```
generic, public :: PreDeclareVariable => &
    DeclareScalarInt, &
    DeclareArray2dInt, &
    DeclareScalarReal, &
    DeclareArray2dReal, ...
```
- Heavy use of templating using jinja
 - E.g. 20 different implementations: scalar, 1-4 dimensional arrays for real, double, int, long, logical. Example:


```
subroutine DeclareArray{{dim}}d{{name}}(this, name, value) ...
  {% for i in range(1, dim+1) %}
  retval = CheckError(nf90_def_dim(this%ncid, name/"dim%{{i}}", &
                                size(value,{{i}}), dimid{{i}}))
  {% endfor %}
```

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Required Manual Work

- The PSyData API defines two calls `<type> PSyDataInit`, `<type> PSyDataShutdown` to be called at start and end of program.
 - De-facto only required in for simple_timing and Vernier profiling API
- `<type>` is (for now) one of `profile`, `read_only_verify`, `value_range_check`, `extract`
- This allows several different PSyData libraries to be linked at the same time
- ~~The config file specified the valid types~~
 - ~~If you add a new type, update the config file~~
- You have to link with the corresponding library in `PSYCLONE_ROOT/lib/...`
 - In LFRic, we just copy the f90 source files into the build tree (with Makefiles, and Fab script automatically adds this file)

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Using PSyData

- Command-line option for profiling:
 - `--profile kernels/--profile invokes`
 - Automatically inserts the required calls for profiling (no variables, only `PreStart` and `PostEnd`)
 - `kernels` adds this to around each loop for a kernel call
 - `invokes` includes all kernels in each invoke
- All other are transformations that need to be applied by a script
 - I might add a better command line interface in the future

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Provide Variables?

- What determines which variables are provided?
- The transformation does. E.g.:
 - Profiling trans: no variable (and as a special case only `PreStart/PostEnd` calls)
 - Value Range Check: all input variables before and output variables after
 - Read-Only check: all variables declared as read, before and after
 - Extraction: read and read-write variables before, write/readwrite variables at end
 - Since the same variable might be provided before and after (readwrite variable):
 - The input value has the name of the variable, the output variable the name with “_post” attached, e.g. `field` and `field_post`
 - Allows comparison of output values, e.g. after a kernel call, `field` should be the same as `field_post`

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Documentation

- User point of view:
https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/psy_data.html
- Developer (of a PSyData library):
https://psyclone-dev.readthedocs.io/en/latest/psy_data.html

Documentation is awaiting PR to include Value Range Check

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Hands-on 2.12

- This example contains three Makefiles:
 - Makefile for profiling
 - Makefile.value_range_check
 - Makefile.extraction (needs NetCDF)
 - You need to `make clean` when switching makefiles
- Add a print statement to view the schedule. What does any of the PSyData transformations do?
- Look at the source code created for the PSy-layer, and see the differences between profile, value_range_check, and extract

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Extraction Example

- Running the example will create a file `psy_time_step_...compute-r0.nc`
- Check the netcdf file with `ncdump`
- The extraction transformation will also create a driver program
- Check what the driver is doing
 - See if you can recognise the PSy-layer contained in the driver ☺
- Compile the driver: `make -f Makefile.extraction driver`
 - Limited support for MPI (one file per rank)
- Run the driver:

```
Variable      max_abs      max_rel      l2_diff      l2_cos      identical ...
  born .0000000E+00 .0000000E+00 .0000000E+00 .1000000E+01 .1690000E+03
  current .0000000E+00 .0000000E+00 .0000000E+00 .1000000E+01 .1690000E+03
```

- Instead of instrumenting all, you could apply the transformation for each kernel
 - If we wouldn't have bug #1611 in Gocean ... which adds all kernels to a driver ☺

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9.2 PSyclone Instrumentation Interface - Hands-on

In this session we will test some of the plugin infrastructure that PSyclone provides. There are two components that play together: first there is a transformation that needs to be applied. Then the application must be linked with the runtime library corresponding to the applied transformation. We will use three different runtime libraries as examples.

Each runtime library requires to call a initialisation and shutdown function, which needs to be added manually to the main program. Here the modifications that have been applied to `gol.f90`:

```
USE profile_psy_data_mod, only: profile_PSyDataInit, &
                               profile_PSyDataShutdown

call profile_PSyDataInit()
! Read in the initial condition into the field 'current',
! and initialise dl_esm_inf.
call read_config(grid, initial, time_steps)

call time_step(grid, initial, time_steps)
call profile_PSyDataShutdown()
```

9.2.1 Profiling Kernels

Profiling is a very frequent task, and as such offers a command line option to simplify its application. You can use `--profile kernels` to add a profiling region around each individual kernel call (even if several kernels are contained in one invoke). Using `--profile invokes` will add a profiling region around each invoke only (which might contain several kernel calls).

Note that applying custom transformation scripts might break the command line options, since it could result that the profiling regions are applied to an invalid location, e.g. inside a `omp parallel do` directive.

Todo

Modify the Makefile to apply each one of the two command line options one after another. See the differences in the code being added to the psy-layer `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90`. Look at the calls added in each case.

Then run the executable with the larger glider configuration. The output when profiling kernels looks like this (note that the regio names have been shortened so that the output fits in one row):

```
=====
module::region      count  sum      min      average      max
count_neighbours_code:r0  2000  14.2656250  0.00000000  7.13281240E-03  3.12500000E-02
compute_born_code:r1      2000  11.9218750  0.00000000  5.96093759E-03  3.12500000E-02
compute_die_code:r2      2000  10.0937500  0.00000000  5.04687522E-03  3.12500000E-02
combine_code:r3         2000  12.0937500  0.00000000  6.04687491E-03  3.12500000E-02
=====
```

Profiling invokes in this case give less useful information:

```
=====
module::region      count  sum      min      average      max
invoke_compute:r0   2000  36.8906250  1.56250000E-02  1.84453130E-02  4.68750000E-02
=====
```

```
invoke_combine_code:r1 2000 11.2187500 0.00000000 5.60937496E-03 3.12500000E-02
=====
```

The current setup uses a small, stand-alone timer library included with PSyclone, which does not require an external profiling library to be added. PSyclone provides interfaces to DrHook, the NVIDIA Tools Extension library (NVTX), the LFRic-timer (the timer functionality included in LFRic), the Tuning and Analysis Utilities Tau (<https://www.cs.uoregon.edu/research/tau/home.php>), and dl_timer (https://bitbucket.org/apeg/dl_timer). If you have any of these libraries available, you only need to modify the compiler options to point to the right PSyclone wrapper library, and in the linking step add the wrapper library and your profiling library. Additional interfaces to other profiling tools can easily be implemented.

Many profiling tools offer the option to instrument your source code directly. The disadvantage of this feature is that with the way kernels are implemented (as functions that operate on a single element), profiling overhead would be added to each individual element, which can prevent vectorisation, and certainly adds significant overhead, which can impact the precision of the timing results. As example, in small LFRic configurations the runtime nearly doubled when instrumenting each individual kernel, since the actual runtime of each kernel is very short.

9.2.2 Value Range Checking

PSyclone comes with a PSyData library that can automatically check that kernel parameters are within a user-specified range. For example, variables (including fields) that represent a fraction, can be tested to be between 0 and 1. In our "Game of Life" example, we can verify that the number of neighbours should be between 0 and 8, and the fields die and born should be between 0 and 1. Additionally, this transform will also verify that the values are not infinity or NAN.

You need to apply the `ValueRangeCheck` transformation from `psyclone.psyir.transformations`. It is important to apply this transformation to the outer loop and not to the kernel itself - if you would apply it to the kernel itself, any variable (including arrays) will get checked each time the kernel is called, not just once before it is called. So instead of looping over all kernels in an `invoke`, you can loop over all `Loops` and select loops that are an outer loop:

```
...
for loop in schedule.walk(GOLoop):
    # Only apply to the outer loop, PSyData will
    # get full arrays provided to check for NANs
    if loop.loop_type == "outer":
        # apply transformation to `loop`
```

A value range is specified using environment variables starting with `PSYVERIFY`. Valid ranges for a variable can be specified in three ways:

```
PSYVERIFY_psy_time_step_alg_mod_invoke_compute_r0__neighbours=0:8
PSYVERIFY_psy_time_step_alg_mod__neighbours=0:8
PSYVERIFY__neighbours=0:8
```

The first one will check the variables `neighbours` in the module `psy_time_step_alg_mod` when calling the kernel `invoke_compute_r0`. The second specification above will check the variable for any kernel call in the module `psy_time_step_alg_mod`. The third way finally will check the variable in any kernel (that is instrumented by the value range check transformation). Besides upper and lower limit as shown above, you can also use `0 :` for a value of 0 and larger, and `: 8` for a value less than or equal 8.

Note that PSyclone adds unique region numbers (`-r0`) to the names to avoid potential name clashes. If required, you can look up the names in the psy-layer file `time_step_alg_mod_psy.f90` - the first call (to `PreStart`) contains the module and region name:

```
CALL value_range_check_psy_data %
     PreStart("psy_time_step_alg_mod",
             "invoke_compute-r0", 5, 3)
```

When setting the environment variables, any “-” must be replaced with an underscore (“_”).

With the setting above, no messages will be printed, but you can see the effect of the value checking by setting e.g. an upper limit of 4:

```
PSYVERIFY__neighbours=0:4
```

Running the example will then produce the following output (in each timestep):

```
PSyData: Variable 'neighbours' has the value 5.0000000000000000 at index/indices 7 8 in
module 'psy_time_step_alg_mod' region 'invoke_compute-r0', which is not between
'0.0000000000000000' and '4.0000000000000000'.
PSyData: Variable 'neighbours' has the value 5.0000000000000000 at index/indices 7 8 in
module 'psy_time_step_alg_mod' region 'invoke_compute-r1', which is not between
'0.0000000000000000' and '4.0000000000000000'.
PSyData: Variable 'neighbours' has the value 5.0000000000000000 at index/indices 7 8 in
module 'psy_time_step_alg_mod' region 'invoke_compute-r2', which is not between
'0.0000000000000000' and '4.0000000000000000'.
```

In order to use the NAN testing that is part of the value range check, you need to modify the source code to produce an infinity or NAN result. This directory contains a modified version of `compute_born`, which will use:

```
born(i, j) = 1.0 / (i-j)
```

This will trigger a division by 0 for all elements on the diagonal. It will only be used by `Makefile.value_range_check!`

Running this version will now produce the following errors at runtime:

```
PSyData: Variable 'current' has the invalid value 'Inf' at index/indices 4 4 in module
'psy_time_step_alg_mod' region 'invoke_compute-r0'.
PSyData: Variable 'neighbours' has the invalid value 'Inf' at index/indices 3 3 in
module 'psy_time_step_alg_mod' region 'invoke_compute-r0'.
```

It indicates which invoke and kernel caused the error, what the invalid value was (`Inf`), the indices at which the error occurred (4 4 etc).

You will notice that there are now a lot more calls inserted by the value range check transformation compared with the profile transformation. This is because the API specifies a declaration of all variables, then provide the values of variables before and after the actual kernel call. You can find additional details in the *PSyclone Developer Guide*, which is especially useful if you want to implement your own runtime library.

9.2.3 Kernel Data Extraction

Kernel data extraction describes a very useful and new ability of PSyclone. Applying the kernel extraction transformation will insert PSyData calls around kernels or invokes. The runtime library uses this to create a NetCDF file at runtime, which stores all input- and output-parameters of the included kernel calls. This transformation can also create a stand-alone driver - a program which will read the written NetCDF file, executes the kernel(s), and then compares the result. This allows you to automatically develop unit tests, or to optimise

the implementation of a single kernel, without having to rerun the full application every time.

The transformation `GOceanExtractTrans` is used to add the data extraction code to a region of code and to create the driver. It takes two optional parameters that can be specified in the options argument - if a driver should be created (default is `False` at this stage), and a tuple containing a module and region name. While PSyclone will create names for you, they are often not intuitive, so you have an option to specify a module and region name to use. The following line enables the creation of a driver program, and also defines the module- and region-name:

```
... apply(..., options={"create_driver": True,
                        "region_name": ("timestep",
                                       "myinvoke")})
```

Typically you might want to extract more than one kernel at a time (it is often used for all kernels in an application, e.g. for LFRic's gungho application over 1600 kernels are created, though only around 400 are executed when running the example configuration), so naming all kernels manually becomes impossible. PSyclone will add region and invoke numbers if required to make sure unique names are created. For this exercise it is recommended to not specify a name to get used of the automatic PSyclone naming scheme.

Todo

In the PSyclone script `extraction.py`, add the required parameter in the options dictionary when calling `apply`. The code can be compiled by using `Makefile`.
extraction:

```
make -f Makefile.extraction
```

After compilation, run the binary:

```
gol.extraction ../gol-lib/config.glider.
```

You should now see that a new file `psy_time_step_alg_mod-invoke_compute-r0.nc` has been created. The added `r0` is a region number added automatically by PSyclone (in case that you instrument more than one kernel).

You can use:

```
ncdump psy_time_step_alg_mod-invoke_compute-r0.nc | less
```

to look at the content of this file. You can see that the dimensions of each field are specified, as well as the data of each field. Fields that input- and output-parameters will actually have two entries in that file. An example is the field `current`: The first entry is called `current`, the other one `current_post`. This field is an input-parameter, because it contains the initial state of the grid, and it is an output-parameter, since its status is being updated at the end. Some parameters are (maybe unexpected) output parameters: `die` and `born` for example. While technically they are only temporary work arrays, they are written first (so they are not input parameters), and any written variable is considered an output, and so will be stored in the file.

The output values of any variable (i.e. the ones with a `post` attached to the names) will be used to verify the computation of the kernel.

The driver program is called `driver-psy_time_step_alg_mod-invoke_compute-r0.F90` (reflecting the name of the created NetCDF file) and you can have a look

at the code created by PSyclone. After a sequence of reading in the data from the file, you will see:

```
...
do j = current_internal_ystart, current_internal_ystop, 1
  do i = current_internal_xstart, current_internal_xstop, 1
    call combine_code(i, j, current, die, born)
  enddo
enddo
call compare_init(6)
call compare('born', born, born_post)
call compare('current', current, current_post)
call compare('die', die, die_post)
call compare('i', i, i_post)
call compare('j', j, j_post)
call compare('neighbours', neighbours, neighbours_post)
call compare_summary()
```

The nested loops are the psy-layer code that calls the kernel. Notice that the driver is not using any field data types, it is using plain Fortran arrays and non-structured scalar types, so it can be used stand-alone without dependencies to the infrastructure library. Also, all required modules for executing the driver are all included in the driver program, so it is truly standalone and does not need any additional dependencies, except NetCDF.

The kernel call is followed by a sequence of correctness tests as shown above.

Todo

You can compile and link the driver (which needs the original kernel object files) using

```
make -f Makefile.extraction driver
```

If you execute the binary, it will print information about all output variables:

```
current correct
i correct
j correct
```

While it might be surprising that it also checks the loop variables `i` and `j`, from PSyclone's point of view these are variables that are modified by the code (which includes the loops), and as such need to be tested.

Note that the extraction transformation can be applied to a list of kernels at the same time (as long as they are consecutive), and the driver will call all kernels. Result checking though will only happen after all kernels have been called, not after each individual kernel.

There are two additional restrictions you need to be aware of:

- If a kernel is called multiple times, the NetCDF file will be overwritten each time the kernel is called, only the data of the last run will be preserved. We are looking at supporting to only store the data for a specific invocation (e.g. say only store the file after the 10th call).
- Distributed memory (MPI) is not fully supported. Each process will write to its own NetCDF file by using its rank, and the created driver can be used with any of the outputfiles, but the driver itself is not MPI parallelised.

10. More Details about PSyclone

This chapter introduces some convenient functionality. It also introduces PSyclone's symbol table. The latter is useful if a transformation script needs to create additional variables, which should not be the same as a variable used by the program.

The hands-on sessions aims at creating a more generic loop fusion script.

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Disadvantage of Most Scripts Written So Far

- Very limited use, specific for a certain file.
- You can typically identify these bad scripts by the usage of constants:
 - `fuse.apply(schedule[0], schedule[1])`
 - `omp_do.apply(schedule[0])`
- Inlining is much better:
for kern in schedule.walk(GOKern):
 `inline.apply(kern)`

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Better?

- Our 'combined OpenMP' script was in between:

```
for loop in schedule.walk(GOLoop):
    if loop.loop_type == "outer":
        omp_do.apply(loop)
omp_parallel.apply(schedule)
```
- The last command would still fail if the schedule contains a halo exchange node, for OpenMP we had to exclude the first halo exchange call:

```
omp_parallel.apply(schedule[1:3])
```

 - Even worse, it might end up creating a race condition
 - We exclude some nodes (halo exchange, return, CodeBlock), but not all

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Details of PSyIR Tree

- Each node as a parent attribute
- Each PSyIR node has a `children` attribute with all children
 - Note that this often includes unexpected children, e.g. in loop: start/stop/step value, not only the loop body.
 - Most (all?) nodes have specific names to access children, e.g.: `loop.loop_body` etc
 - `Node.children` IS the tree information – if you modify this list, you will modify the tree!
 - Often you want to take a copy of the children list (so e.g. you can remove nodes from the list without affecting the tree)
- Use `node.walk(some_class)` to find nodes
 - Can also take a list of classes
- Use `isinstance()` to check if you have the right node

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More Useful PSyIR Functions

- You can use `node.siblings` (attribute) to get all nodes on the same level
 - Includes node itself
- Closest ancestor of a given class:
 - `node.ancestor(Statement)`
- Each node has a position, which is the index in the child list of the parent.
Can be used to get the next/previous node:
 - `node.parent.children[node.position+1]`
Assuming of course that there is a next node ☺
- For debugging: remember you can get a textual representation of the tree using:
 - `print(node.view())`
 - `print(node)` is a not that useful, flat view

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Modifying the Tree

- PSyclone has consistency checks:
 - E.g. you can't attach a node that is still attached elsewhere.
 - Call `node.detach()` first
- Removing all children:
`unattached_children = node.pop_all_children()`
- You can copy a sub-tree
 - `node.copy()`
- Handy shortcut to replace a node:
 - `old_node.replace_with(new_node)`

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Schedule

- A `Schedule` is a 'basic block' of the language, a list of statements with one parent
 - E.g. body of a subroutine, loop body, the code in an `if` or `else` block.
- A `Schedule` is a `ScopingNode`
 - I.e. it has a symbol table
 - Fortran does not support nested Symbol Tables (in C you can declare variables anywhere)
 - When converting the PSyIR to Fortran, symbols will be renamed as required
- You can find the closest scoping node using:
 - `node.scope.symbol_table`

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Symbols

- Any variable in the PSyIR is a `Reference`
 - And it has a `symbol` attribute, which is in the `SymbolTable`
- Each symbol has some useful attributes:
 - `symbol.is_array` – if a variable is an array or not (careful with derived types)
 - `symbol.datatype` – the type of a variable
 - `symbol.interface` - Where a symbol is coming from:
 - `ArgumentInterface` – it's an argument
 - `ImportInterface` – imported from a module
 - `AutomaticInterface` – local variable
 - `StaticInterface` – 'save' attribute
 - `UnknownInterface` – there is a declaration, but psyclone doesn't support it (e.g. pointer)
 - `UnresolvedInterface` – there is a symbol, but no declaration

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SymbolTable

- Mostly invisible (i.e. not shown in tree view)
- Declaring variables is a complicated undertaking


```
use constants_mod, only: r_def
real(kind=r_def)         :: one
```

 - Involves already four symbol type:
 - `ContainerSymbol`, `DataSymbol`, `DataType`, `ScalarSymbol`
- Not to mention public/private, allocatable, dimension
 - Routines are a `RoutineSymbol` (pure, elemental)
 - Then think of derived types
- Typically, not necessary to look into details, parsing will do this for you
 - `symbol_table.new_symbol()`, `find_or_create()`, `lookup()`

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Some Useful Tips

- Avoiding conflicts when you need to create a variable
 - The user's program might contain whatever name you use.
- Any symbol in a symbol table is unique
- Solution: Symbols in the symbol table can have a 'tag' (string)
 - A tag is unique, and its associated symbol is guaranteed to be unique (but can be different from the tag)
- Order is important:
 - First add symbols from existing program, then add tags
- Symbol table lookup and add functions come with tag variations
 - `find_or_create_tag()`, `lookup_with_tag()`

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Transformations

- Each transformation validates if it is safe to apply a transformation
 - There are known and unknown bugs ☹
- You can call `transform.validate(...)` to check if a transformation can be applied
- Will raise `TransformationError` if it is invalid to transform
 - No change the the PSyIR tree
 - If an error during `apply()` (i.e. not from `validate()`) – please submit a bug report
 - Since at this stage the PSyIR tree might be inconsistent
 - Examples so far been bad by not catching `TransformationError`
- The transformation will contain more details:
 - `print("Cannot apply transformation. Error: ", str(err.value))`
- You can use get the name of a transformation: `transform.name`

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Options for Transformations

- Each transformation takes an 'option' dictionary, with additional settings
 - Eg. loop fuse has an option to disable dependency tests
 - Sometimes a user knows better than PSyclone

```
fuse = GOceanLoopFuseTrans()
fuse.apply(node1, node2, option={"force": True})
```
- Reason is that we might have nested transformation, $a \rightarrow b \rightarrow c$, and we might need an option for c, which is invalid/unknown at a.
 - We need to make sure each option has a unique name of course ☹
 - Which we admittedly don't do atm ... but then, we don't really have nested transformations either ☺

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Hands-on 2.18

- Write a more generic loop fuse script:
 1. Find all outer loops
 2. For each outer loop:
 1. check if the next node is also an outer loop
 2. If so, check if it is valid to fuse them
 3. If it is, continue with 2.1
- Bonus points
 - Use same script to then fuse inner loops
- That might take some time to get it right

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11.2 More details about PSyclone - hands-on

Directory: PSyclone/tutorial/training/gocean/2.18-GameOfLife-IntelligentScripts

In this session the user should try to implement a more generic loop fusion script. Ideally it should handle nested loop, and it should first try to merge outer loops, then the inner loops.

This session is rather open ended, but the solutions subdirectory contains two different approaches to fuse as many loop as possible.

11. Using PSyclone with Existing Fortran Code

So far, we have been using PSyclone's code generation / domain-specific language capabilities to create the PSyIR tree, which is then transformed. But PSyclone can also be used to modify existing Fortran code. For example, the ocean model NEMO is switching to include NEMO in their build system, which allows them to add support for OpenMP and GPUs without source code modification.

The hands-on session will use a modified version of the Game of Life example used so far. But instead of using `invoke` and let PSyclone create the loops, the loops are written, and therefore this code represents existing Fortran code that is modified.

11.1 Using Pysyclone with Existing Fortran Code - Slides

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Basic Code Creation

- As indicated earlier, we have various backend that creates valid Fortran (and other) source code from a PSyIR
- But there seems to be a small inconsistency:
 - A single PSyData node is inserted into the tree
 - Output Fortran code contains many Fortran statements:

```
GOInvokeSchedule[invoke='invoke_compute']
0: Extract[]
  Schedule[]
    0: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space=...]
    ...
    Schedule[]
      0: Loop[type='inner', field_space='go_ct', it_space=...]
        Schedule[]
          0: CodedKern
          1: Loop[type='outer', field_space='go_ct', it_space=...]
```

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Code Created

```
CALL extract_psy_data % PreStart("psy_time_step_alg mod", &
                                "invoke_compute-r0", 17, 6)
CALL extract_psy_data % PreDeclareVariable("born%internal%xstart", &
                                           born % internal % xstart)
CALL extract_psy_data % PreDeclareVariable("born%internal%xstop", &
                                           born % internal % xstop)
...
CALL extract_psy_data % ProvideVariable("neighbours%internal%ystop",
                                       neighbours % internal % ystop)
CALL extract_psy_data % PreEnd
DO j = neighbours%internal%ystart, neighbours%internal%ystop, 1
  DO i = neighbours%internal%xstart, neighbours%internal%xstop, 1
    CALL count_neighbours_code(i, j, neighbours%data, &
                              current%data)
  END DO
END DO
```

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More PSyIR

- There are two flavours of PSyIR:
 - Domain-specific PSyIR
 - Language-level PSyIR
- The domain-specific PSyIR can be 'lowered' to become the language-level PSyIR
 - The lowering will replace domain-specific nodes with explicit call, e.g.:
 - kernel becomes a call
 - PSyData node becomes a list of calls
- The extraction node has a `lower_to_language_level()` method, which will replace itself with a schedule of all the required calls
 - All PSyData nodes actually only provide a list of variables to the PSyData base class, which does everything else

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Why Domain-specific PSyIR?

- The domain-specific nodes have more information
- For example, in case of a GOcean kernel we know:
 - It only writes any field to `field(i,j)`
 - We know which values are read and the access stencil
 - Important to verify certain loop transformations
 - We know loop boundaries (meta-data include on which fields a kernel operates)
 - We know that two different variables on the same field type have the same size
 - Lowering loses (some) information
- In case of a call, typically we know nothing about parameters
 - And if we start to follow call trees, it gets complicated ☹
- Many transformations/tools work with both PSyIR styles
 - But might work better with domain-specific PSyIR

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Transformation of Existing Fortran Code

- We can use the PSyclone transformations on existing Fortran codes
 - You will just see slightly different nodes (e.g. Kern in a DSL, a call with generic codes)
- Transformation scripts might work with both flavours
 - Useful to e.g. check for base classes:

```
from psyclone.goceanlp0 import GOLoop → from psyclone.psyir.nodes import Loop
for loop in schedule.walk(GOLoop):    → for loop in schedule.walk(Loop):
```
- Invoke PSyclone without `-api` parameter
 - In PSyclone 2.5 this was called the NEMO API and required `-api nemo`
 - The transformation script will receive the top level PSyIR
 - Consistent with `lfri`/`gocean` domains now
- Output filename: use `-o` (not `-opsy` or `-oalg`)

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Generic PSyIR

```

FileContainer[time_step_mod.x90]
  Container[time_step_mod]
    Routine[name:'time_step']
      0: Assignment[]
        Reference[name:'neighbours']
        ArrayReference[name:'r2d_field']
          Reference[name:'grid']
          Reference[name:'go_t_points']

```

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PSyIR Nodes

- There are many different nodes type
 - Can't cover them all here.
 - The documentation is (imho, admittedly I am biased) pretty good:
 - <https://psyclone-ref.readthedocs.io/en/latest/autogenerated/psyclone.psyir.nodes.html>
 - Remember to click on parent classes in the inheritance diagrams
 - E.g. `FileContainer` is mostly empty, the useful features come from `Container`
- Declarations are not shown in the PSyIR
 - Certain PSyIR nodes (anything based on `ScopingNode`) have a symbol table
 - This symbol table is used when converting PSyIR to source code
 - More details later

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Transformations

- Transformations on generic PSyIR mostly identical to DSL-specific ones
- In some cases, there are domain-specific implementations, e.g.:
 - `psyir.transformations.LoopFuseTrans`
 - `domain.gocean.GOceanLoopFuse`
 - `Domain.lfric.LFRicLoopFuseTrans`
- The domain-specific ones inherit from the generic ones
 - But typically add domain-specific validation methods
 - Example:
 - In GOcean we know from meta-data what the loop boundaries are
 - They are taken from the field
 - Generic loop boundary checks will not know that different fields have same boundaries
- No easy way of knowing which transform to use (i.e. specific or generic) ☹
 - On my todo list

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Local and Global Validation Checks

- PSyclone will validate transformation
 - Make sure we never create incorrect code
 - Sometimes the user might have to disable validation (user know more than PSyclone can)
- Some validations will happen at code creation time only
 - When adding `omp parallel`, there should be a `parallel` construct inside
 - When adding `omp do`, there should be an enclosing `omp parallel`
- Chicken-egg problem:
 - you can't add the `do` before the `parallel`
 - You can't add the `parallel` without the `do`
- Global validation is done when converting the final PSy-IR to source code

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Orphaned OpenMP Directives

- Global validation does not work with orphaned OpenMP directives:

```
!$omp parallel default(shared)
  call count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  call compute_born(born, current, neighbours)
  ...
!$omp end parallel
```

- And:

```
!$omp do schedule(auto)
  do j = ystart, ystop, 1
```

- Solution: Command line option to disable global validation:

```
--backend disable-validation
```

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Inference Rules

- Coding style in code often determines loop type
 - E.g. in NEMO: jk loops are levels, jj loops are latitudes, ji longitudinal points
- Instead of hard-coding the variable names in the scripts, you can give loops a 'type' based on the variable name

- Easier to understand and more portable scripts:

```
if loop.variable.name == "jk": → if loop.type == "level":
```

```
from psyclone.psyir.nodes import Loop
Loop.set_loop_type_inference_rules({
    "lon": {"variable": "ji"},
    "lat": {"variable": "jj"},
    "levels": {"variable": "jk"},
    "tracers": {"variable": "jt"} })
```

- ATM only 'variable' is allowed as rule

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Hands-on 3.2

- Source code mostly same version as hands-on 2.2.
- It is using `dl_esm_inf` for data structures
 - Could be using standard Fortran arrays
- The compute kernels have all been renamed to be `.x90`
 - This is just to make it easy to decide for which files to use PSyclone, there is not DSL-specific feature (`invoke` etc) in these files
 - Also makes the makefile rules easier (`.x90` → `.f90` → `.o`)

• *(I intend to change this tutorial to use Fortran arrays and no `.x90` files)*

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Hands-on .../training/transformation/3.2

- Apply OpenMP parallelisation to the original Game of Life
 - Apply `omp parallel do` to all kernels
 - Start with using `omp_trans.py` as template
 - Very similar to the example when using GOcean
 - Will not be very performant, since each kernel starts and shuts-down the threads
- Improvement:
 - Add `omp parallel` into time stepping loop
 - Add only `omp do` to kernels
 - Use `omp_parallel.py` as template
 - It uses the filename to distinguish what transformation to apply
 - `omp parallel` vs `omp do`

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Using Filenames in Scripts

- Typically (see LFRic build system) you would have different scripts for different files
- But with very complex and intelligent scripts, you might want to avoid code duplication
 - For NEMO (OpenMP and GPU), we are using file names and subroutines names frequently
 - Disable transformation because
 - They are buggy (compiler or PSyclone)
 - Would not perform well
 - We use file- and subroutine-names frequently with NEMO to disable/enable transformations
- Alternatively, clever OO design of scripts?

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11.3 Using PSyclone with Existing Fortran Code - Hands-On

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/transformation/3.2](https://github.com/psyclone/tutorial/training/transformation/3.2)

This directory contains a copy of the very first version of the Game of Life, written in standard Fortran without any DSL-specific features (though it is still using `dl_esm_inf`).

In this exercise you will first add OpenMP directives around the four compute kernels. These files have been renamed to have the `.x90` extension, but this is done to keep the Makefile similar between exercises, you can easily use the standard `.f90` extension (but then you have to create new output files for the processed files, and these names then need to be used in the Makefile).

11.3.1 Using OMP Parallel Do

Similarly to exercise 2.8, you can start with just adding OpenMP Parallel Do statements. The script `omp_trans.py` is available, but you need to specify the loop-type inference rules. Then you can use the loop type to only parallel latitudinal (or outer) loops.

In case of using PSyclone's transformation only usage, the command line options are slightly different from the dsl-specific ones, more aligned to typical options used by a compiler:

```
psyclone -l output -nodm -s ./omp_trans.py
          -o count_neighbours_mod.f90
          count_neighbours_mod.x90
```

11.3.2 Using OMP Parallel and OpenMP Do

Again, using a single OpenMP parallel statement, and include several OMP Do loops should in general result in better performance, since the overhead of starting and synchronising threads is reduced. This was easy to achieve in the GOcean approach of the Game of Life, since all loop were contained in the same subroutine. But with this application, the calls to the kernels are actually in `time_step_mod.x90`, but the loops are in the individual subroutines.

Todo

Using the script `omp_parallel.py` as a starting point, add an OpenMP parallel around all calls in the time stepping loop, and individual `omp do` statements around any loop. When running PSyclone on `combine_mod.x90`, you have to use:

```
psyclone -l output -nodm -s ./omp_parallel.py -o
combine_mod.f90 \
combine_mod.x90
```

Otherwise, PSyclone will detect the usage of OMP do without an enclosing parallel construct:

```
psyclone.errors.GenerationError: Generation Error:  
OMPDoDirective must be inside an OMP parallel region  
but could not find an ancestor OMPParallelDirective node
```

12. Inlining, Move and Loop Tiling

This section introduces transformations to do proper inlining for generic Fortran code. At this stage, proper inlining of a subroutine is only supported in generic Fortran, LFRic and GOcean do not yet support this. It also explains a transformation that moves nodes in the PSyIR tree. Finally, it also introduces loop tiling. Loop tiling, which will be explained in more detail, can significantly improve cache usage for certain loops.

The hands-on session combines all these transformations to optimise a generic implementation of the Game of Life. The full implementation of this is quite complex and time consuming, and it is recommended to attempt this outside of the training.

12.1 Inlining, Move, and Loop Tiling - Slides

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Some More Useful Transformations

- Introduce some more complex, but useful transformation
- See <https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/transformations.html> for a complete overview

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Inlining

- The last part of the previous hands-on session showed some limitations when modifying code
 - And even though OpenMP worked, we can't fuse loops, without a major refactoring:


```
!$omp parallel default(shared)
  call count_neighbours(neighbours, current)
  call compute_born(born, current, neighbours)
...

```
- Psyclone's Inlining Transformation can bring all the loops together
 - Inlining: (kind of) replace the call of a subroutine with the content of the subroutine
- Inlining is quite difficult, and there are quite a few restrictions
 - Doesn't work with GOcean or LFRic (due to type checks of variables, ... long story ☹ - but we are getting there)

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Inlining Transformation

```
from psyclone.psyir.transformations import InlineTrans
...
inline = InlineTrans()
for call in psyir.walk(Call):
    inline.apply(call)
```

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Example Output

```
do time = 1, time_steps, 1
  xstart = current%internal%xstart
  xstop = current%internal%xstop
  ystart = current%internal%ystart
  ystop = current%internal%ystop
  do j = ystart, ystop, 1
    do i = xstart, xstop, 1
      neighbours%data(i,j) = current%data(i - 1,j - 1)...
    enddo
  enddo
  xstart_1 = current%internal%xstart
  ...
  do j_1 = ystart_1, ystop_1, 1
    do i_1 = xstart_1, xstop_1, 1...
```

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Inlining and Symbols

- Inlining makes sure to create new symbols
 - Avoid name clashes, potential modifying a variable:


```
a = 3
call some_sub(field)    ! Which uses a local variable 'a'
field = field + a
```
- That can make loop inference hard/impossible
 - Maybe we should support regular expressions in the inference rules? "i.*": "lon"
- Outer loops can be identified differently
 - It has a loop as loop body

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Move Transformation

- Allows to move a statement to a different location
 - Verifies that no dependencies are changed

```
do i = 1, n          ! ← target_node
...
scalar = 3          ! ← node_to_move
do i = 1, n
```

```
from psyclone.transformations import MoveTrans, TransformationError
move = MoveTrans()
move.apply(node_to_move, target_node, options={"position": "before"})

scalar = 3          ! ← node_to_move
do i = 1, n          ! ← target_node
...
do i = 1, n
```

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Loop Tiling

- Stencil access:
- With long lines, data in upper rows will not be in cache

	1	2	3	4
1	1	2	3	4
2	2	4	6	8
3	3	6	9	12
4	4	8	12	16

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Loop Tiling

- By looping over tiles we can reuse memory in cache
- Can lead to significant speedup
- Compilers' ability to do this seem inconsistent

	1	2	3	4
1	1	2	3	4
2	2	4	6	8
3	3	6	9	12
4	4	8	12	16

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Loop Chunking

- Loop blocking/tiling/chunking tries to improve cache efficiency

```
do j=1, n
  tmp(j) = 2 * tmp(j) - tmp(j-1) - tmp(j+1)
enddo
```

- Blocking by computing 32 elements at a time:

```
do j_out_var = 1, n, 32
  j_el_inner = MIN(j_out_var + (32 - 1), n)
  do j = j_out_var, j_el_inner, 1
    tmp(j) = 2 * tmp(j) - tmp(j-1) - tmp(j+1)
  enddo
enddo
```

- 1D for vectorisation (by compiler)

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2D Stencil Loop

```
do i=1, 100
  do j=1, 100
    tmp(i, j) = 2 * tmp(i, j) - tmp(i, j-1) - tmp(i, j+1)
  enddo
enddo
```

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Tiled 2D Stencil Loop

```
do i_out_var = 1, 100, 32
  i_el_inner = MIN(i_out_var + (32 - 1), 100)
  do j_out_var = 1, 100, 32
    do i = i_out_var, i_el_inner, 1
      j_el_inner = MIN(j_out_var + (32 - 1), 100)
      do j = j_out_var, j_el_inner, 1
        tmp(i,j) = 2 * tmp(i,j) - tmp(i,j-1) - tmp(i,j+1)
      enddo
    enddo
  enddo
enddo
```

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Loop Tiling with PSyclone

- As simple as:

```
from psyclone.psyir.transformations import LoopTiling2DTrans
tiling = LoopTiling2DTrans()
tiling.apply(loop, options={"tilesize": 16})
```

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Hands-on 3.4

- Directory `transformation/3.4`
- Same example as 3.2, but only `time_step_mod.x90` – ‘kernels’ are modified
- First inline all kernels to bring the loops into the same tree
- Study the file structure after inlining, then apply OpenMP
 - Optimised, not just `omp parallel do` for each loop ☺
 - PSyclone is clever and will declare private declarations as required.
- The rest will take too much time, but ideally you want:
 1. Move scalar assignments of loop boundaries to top (so loop are next to each other)
 2. Then you can fuse (some) loops
 - Difficult, since fuse transformation cannot know that loop boundaries (scalars) are identical
 - You would have to replace the loop boundaries to be identical (*I might design transform to help*)
 3. Then you can apply OpenMP, and tiling

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12.2 Inlining and Loop Tiling Hands-on

Directory: PSystem/tutorial/training/transformation/3.4

PSystem does support proper inlining, i.e. replacing a function call with the actual source code of the called function. Inlining a function will reduce the call overhead, and can enable additional compiler optimisations.

At this stage, PSystem does not yet support inlining in case of its domain-specific language support (which is why we have used module inlining previously). But when using PSystem to transform existing code, inlining can be used.

This example is again based on the Game of Life, as in section 3.2, i.e. it does not use the GOcean domain. We have used PSystem to fuse loops previously. But in order to use fusion in this version, we have to bring the loop next to each other, and make sure that the loop boundaries are identical. This full example is rather complex and it is not expected that it can be finished in the typical time of a single hands-on session.

12.2.1 Use the inlining transformation

All subroutine calls except `output_field` need to be inlined. You can use the `walk` method to find all `Calls`, and the name of a routine can be accessed using `call.routine.name`. Make sure to study the code created after inlining:

```
do time = 1, time_steps, 1
  xstart = current%internal%xstart
  xstop = current%internal%xstop
  ystart = current%internal%ystart
  ystop = current%internal%ystop
  do j = ystart, ystop, 1
    do i = xstart, xstop, 1
      neighbours%data(i,j) = current%data(i - 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i,j - 1) + current%data(i + 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i - &
&1,j) + current%data(i + 1,j) + current%data(i - 1,j +
1) + current%data(i,j + 1) + current%data(i + 1,j + 1)
    enddo
  enddo
  xstart_1 = current%internal%xstart
  xstop_1 = current%internal%xstop
  ystart_1 = current%internal%ystart
  ystop_1 = current%internal%ystop
  do j_1 = ystart_1, ystop_1, 1
    do i_1 = xstart_1, xstop_1, 1
      born%data(i_1,j_1) = 0.0
      if (current%data(i_1,j_1) == 0.0 .AND.
neighbours%data(i_1,j_1) == 3.0) then
        born%data(i_1,j_1) = 1.0
      end if
    enddo
  enddo
enddo
```

Each subroutine used the same scalar variables to determine start and stop values of the loops. Inlining will rename variables if there is a clash, so all the assignments (even though they are identical) have been changed.

The immediate problem to do additional code optimisations is that still the loops are not next to each other.

12.2.2 Use the Move transformation

Before any loop fusion can be done, the loops must be next to each other, which means that the scalar assignments must all be moved to the top. This can be done with the Move transformation.

12.2.3 Loop Fusion with a twist

Still, even though the loops are now next to each other, loop fusion still does not work:

```
Transformation Error: Error in LoopFuseTrans
transformation. Loops do not have the same iteration space.
do j = ystart, ystop, 1
  do i = xstart, xstop, 1
    neighbours%data(i,j) = current%data(i - 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i,j - 1) + current%data(i + 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i - 1,j) + current%data(i + 1,j) +
current%data(i - 1,j + 1) + current%data(i,j + 1) +
current%data(i + 1,j + 1)
  enddo
enddo

do j_1 = ystart_1, ystop_1, 1
  do i_1 = xstart_1, xstop_1, 1
    born%data(i_1,j_1) = 0.0
```

Reason is that the first loop uses `ystart`, and the second loop uses `ystart_1` etc. In this case, we know that `ystart` and `ystart_1` are the same, but PSyclone will not automatically deduce this.

The easiest solution is to replace all the scalar values with the values they are getting assigned. When moving the assignments, you can keep the variable name and the assigned values, e.g. in a dictionary. As a reminder, an assignment node has `lhs` and `rhs` attributes.

Then loop over all References, which is the PSyIR node type of a variable access. And if the accessed value is one of the variables assigned previously, replace it with a `copy()` of the value. After this, the loop will look like:

```
do j = current%internal%ystart, current%internal%ystop, 1
  do i = current%internal%xstart, current%internal%xstop,
1
    neighbours%data(i,j) = current%data(i - 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i,j - 1) + current%data(i + 1,j - 1) +
current%data(i - &
&1,j) + current%data(i + 1,j) + current%data(i - 1,j + 1) +
current%data(i,j + 1) + current%data(i + 1,j + 1)
  enddo
enddo
do j_1 = current%internal%ystart, current%internal%ystop,
1
  do i_1 = current%internal%xstart,
```

Inlining, Move and Loop Tiling

```
current%internal%xstop, 1
  born%data(i_1,j_1) = 0.0
  if (current%data(i_1,j_1) == 0.0 .AND.
neighbours%data(i_1,j_1) == 3.0) then
    born%data(i_1,j_1) = 1.0
  end if
enddo
enddo
```

After this step, you can finally fuse the loop.

Optional steps:

Apply OpenMP parallelisation, and then loop tiling. The order in the latter is important, after loop tiling the dependency analysis of PSyclone will not be able to detect if parallelisation is still valid due to the complex, 4-times nested loop structure.

13. Psyclone Tools

This section first shows how PSyclone can be invoked in Python scripts, allowing users to create more complicated scripts and tools than just simple transformations. It starts with converting Fortran source code to PSyIR, and then converting the PSyIR back to Fortran source code by using the PSyclone's Fortran frontend and backend. Then it shows the equivalent tools to convert Fortran expressions to be used with the symbolic maths package SymPy (<https://www.sympy.org/>).

Then it introduces some PSyclone internal tools: the dependency analysis that can be used to determine if loops can be parallelised, or loops be fused. There is also a static call tree analysis, that determines all symbols used in a kernel call recursively, i.e. if function `f1` calls `f2` which calls `f3`, and `f3` reads or writes a module variable `v`, then `v` will be included in this list (either as read or write or both). This is an essential basic functionality for the kernel extraxtion, but can be equally useful for other work (e.g. trying to modify code so that it can work on a GPU).

A more generic tool is used to collect all variables used in a code. The `VariableAccessInfo` class collects information about all variables used in a set of code, including if the variable is read or written, and if the variable is an array, what indices are being used. It can be used to evaluate optimisations for a code. For example, it is used to determine if a loop can be parallelised.

13.1 PSyclone Tools - Slides

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Using PSyclone in Python Scripts

- You can just use PSyclone to get a PSyIR and write it back
 - Basically, explicitly doing what `psyclone -s ...` does internally
- You can see that we use a frontend to convert from Fortran to PSyIR
- And a backend to convert from PSyIR to Fortran
- Anything in between is up to you
 - Including obviously applying transformations
- More work than e.g. just invoking `psyclone` with a scripts
- Can be convenient for some use cases, e.g.
 - Creating different versions of the same subroutine to check which one is fastest

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Template

```
from psyclone.psyir.frontend.fortran import FortranReader
from psyclone.psyir.backend.fortran import FortranWriter

Code = """subroutine foo(a, b)""" # Or read from file, ...
reader = FortranReader()
psyir = reader.psyir_from_source(code)
writer = FortranWriter()
fortran = writer(psyir)
```

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Symbolic Maths

- PSyclone is internally using Sympy (<https://www.sympy.org/>)
 - Dependency analysis – validate if loops can be parallelised
- It provides parser support to convert from Fortran **expressions** to Sympy expressions and back
 - Parsing expressions is a bit more involved than parsing a Fortran subroutine:
 - We need the symbol table
- Afaik PSyclone has the most complete Fortran conversion
 - Support for kind constants (3.14_8)
 - Support for array expressions and derived types (a%b)

- Remember useful method:

```
psyir_node.replace_with(new_node)
```

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From Fortran to SymPy and Back

```
from sympy import simplify
from psyclone.psyir.frontend.sympy_reader import SymPyReader
from psyclone.psyir.backend.sympy_writer import SymPyWriter

math_expr = sympy_writer(psyir) # PSyIR -> Sympy
simple_math = simplify(math_expr) # Use sympy

# Now convert back to PSyIR. We need symbol info from the sympy writer
sympy_reader = SymPyReader(sympy_writer)
# Fortran symbol table required to know about types when parsing expr.
symbol_table = psyir.scope.symbol_table
simple = sympy_reader.psyir_from_expression(simple_math, symbol_table)
```

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Convenient Class

- Class `SymbolicMaths` with useful shortcuts (<https://psyclone-dev.readthedocs.io/en/stable/sympy.html>)
 - `equal`, `never_equal`, `solve_equal_for`, `expand`
- Take PSyIR as parameters, if required converts back to PSyIR

```
sym_maths = SymbolicMaths.get()
sym_maths.expand(assignment.rhs)
```

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Dependency Analysis

- Encapsulates basic concepts from *Kennedy, K. and Allen, J. R. Optimizing Compilers for Modern Architectures A Dependence-Based Approach*
- Two user function: `can_loop_be_parallelised`, `can_loops_be_fused`
- In case of failures, contains a list of messages with details

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```
from psyclone.psyir.tools.dependency_tools import DependencyTools
dt = DependencyTools()
if dt.can_loop_be_parallelised(loop, var):
    parallel_loop_static.apply(statement)
else:
    for message in dt.get_all_messages():
        print(message)
        print("Variable: ", message.var_names)
```

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Variable Access Information

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- Collect information about which variable is used where
 - First step in dependency analysis
 - Used to determine private variables
- Core of many 'intelligent' scripts
- Uses 'Signature' as key of a dictionary.
 - Mostly same as a variable name, but:
 - Supports derived types: a%b%c
 - To get the symbol name of a signature, use signature[0]
- Each statement has a statement number
 - Useful to test 'before' or 'after'
- **Does not understand conditionals!!**

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Usage of Variable Access Info

```

from psyclone.core import VariablesAccessInfo
varinfo = VariablesAccessInfo(psyir_node) # or list of nodes
for signature in varinfo:
    accesses = varinfo[signature]
    print(signature, accesses)
    for written in accesses.all_write_accesses:
        # written.node is typically the Reference, so find the statement
        statement = written.node.ancestor(Statement)
    ...
    
```

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Example Use Case: Dataflow Diagram

```

subroutine foo(a, b)
  real, intent(inout) :: a
  real, intent(inout) :: b
  real :: c, d, e, f
  c = a + 1.0
  e = a**2
  f = cos(e)
  d = c + 2.0
  c = d * a
  b = c + d
  call bar(c, b)
  b = b + c
end subroutine foo
    
```

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Static Calltree Analysis

- Determine input and output parameters of a subroutine
 - In case of kernel uses meta-data
- Can follow the call trees to find all variables
 - Utilises a ModuleManager to find source files
 - Recursive search paths taken from PSyclone's `-d` (kernel path) directives
 - Might require non-kernel-paths (work-in-progress to combine with the `-i` directive)
 - Efficient by caching as much data as possible
 - Esp. `fparser` trees, which are slow to create
- Internally uses the `VariableAccessInfo` class repeatedly
- Is the core of kernel extraction

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Static Calltree Analysis

- Interface:


```
from psyclone.psyir.tools import CallTreeUtils
ctu = CallTreeUtils()
ctu.get_in_out_parameters(self, node_list,
                        collect_non_local_symbols=False,
                        options=None):
```
- Returns:
 - `ReadWriteInfo` object, which has a `read_list` and `write_list`, e.g.:


```
[('', Signature(chi)),
 ('dummy_mod', Signature(dummy_var1)),
 ('testkern_w0_kernel_mod', Signature(some_other_var))]
```
 - Usage of signatures to support derived types

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Hands-on

- Transformation/3.6-sympy
 - Use sympy_test.py
- Create PSyIR from source code in string
- Get variable access information for the subroutine
- Use SymPy to simplify the right-hand-side of the first assignment
- Use SymPy to differentiate the right-hand-side of the second assignment

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13.2 Psyclone Tools - Hands-on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/transformation/3.6-sympy](https://github.com/psyclone/tutorial/tree/master/training/transformation/3.6-sympy)

This hands-on session uses just two stand-alone Python programs, and is not using the Game of Life at all. These Python programs contain simple Fortran programs, assigned to a string variable.

13.2.1 Read and write Fortran source code

Start with using `handle_fortran.py`. Add the code that converts Fortran source code to PSyIR, and then convert the PSyIR back to a string.

13.3 Collecting Variable Access Information

This exercise shows the usage of the `VariableAccessInformation` class. Use the program `var_access.py`, and fill in the code to collect access information for the whole PSyIR. It already contains code to print out the accesses for all variables. Example output:

```
Variable Access Info - Summary:
a: READ, b: READWRITE, c: READWRITE, d: READ+WRITE, e:
READ+WRITE, f: WRITE
=====

a : a:READ(0),READ(1),READ(4)
-----
Type: READ - location 0 - node Reference[name:'a']
Type: READ - location 1 - node Reference[name:'a']
Type: READ - location 4 - node Reference[name:'a']

c : c:WRITE(0),READ(3),WRITE(4),READ(5),READWRITE(6),
READ(7)
-----
Type: WRITE - location 0 - node Reference[name:'c']
Type: READ - location 3 - node Reference[name:'c']
Type: WRITE - location 4 - node Reference[name:'c']
Type: READ - location 5 - node Reference[name:'c']
Type: READWRITE - location 6 - node Reference[name:'c']
Type: READ - location 7 - node Reference[name:'c']
```

The location is based on locally numbering the statements. So location 0 is the first executable statement (`c = a + 1.0`) etc. The node, which is stored for each access, is typically a `Reference`. You can use the `ancestor` method to find the expressions where the variable is actually used in.

You will find all variable accesses in this list. In the case of a call, the variables are marked as `read` and `write`, since PSyclone does not have any information about the subroutine (without doing additional work).

The solution directory contains a program `dataflow.py`, which uses this information to create `graphviz` code to show a data-flow diagram. It is a small wrapper around the `VariableAccessInformation` class. Given the example code:

```

subroutine foo(a, b)
real, intent(inout) :: a
real, intent(inout) :: b
real :: c, d, e, f
c = a + 1.0
e = a**2
f = cos(e)
d = c + 2.0
c = d * a
b = c + d
call bar(c, b)
b = b + c
end subroutine foo

```

it will create the graph on the right

13.3.1 Using SymPy

The last example uses the program `sympy_test.py`. It allows you to convert a Fortran expression to a SymPy expression, which can be e.g. modified, or used to compute a derivative, and then re-inserted into the Fortran code. This example shows how to add new nodes, including comments.

The example code contains the two assignments:

```

b = a(j + 2*i - j - i, j*3 - 2*j)*a(i, j) + &
    5*b - b - 3*b - 3.14_8
b = 3*x*x - 2*x - 1

```

The example program will explicitly simplify the first assignment. Then it will take the right-hand-side of the second assignment (`3*x*x - 2*x - 1`), compute its derivative, and insert it as an additional assignment to the end:

```

b = b + a(i, j) ** 2 - 3.14
b = 3 * x * x - 2 * x - 1
! The derivative is:
b = 6 * x - 2

```

14. Psyclone's LFRic Domain

This chapter introduces the usage of Psyclone with LFRic, the UK Met Office's next generation numerical weather prediction system. It explains the data structures used in LFRic, and the required meta-data (though due to its complexity, only basic kernel structures are introduced here). Then it introduces the concept of built-ins.

14.1 Psyclone's LFRic Domain - Slides

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LFRic Domain

- Unstructured grid
- One loop (over all cells in the 2D mesh) over all elements
- Each 'element' is a column of the 3D grid
 - Each kernel must operate on a column, i.e. typically contains a loop over the vertical
 - The PSy-layer loops over all cells (in a single loop)
- Infrastructure library is part of LFRic
 - Check `lfric_core/LFRic/infrastructure/source` subdirectory
 - PSyclone contains a stripped-down version of this infrastructure library (e.g. no MPI support)
 - Sufficient for unit testing, examples, and training

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Function Spaces

- Different function spaces, e.g.:
 - W0: blue vertices
 - W1: edge (not shown)
 - W2: face (not shown)
 - W3: red dots for a cell
 - There are a few more
- Each field is for one of the function spaces
 - Function space determines field size

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Basis Function Order

- In FE, the actual value is a combination of basis functions, and they can come in different orders
- In our examples, we will be using order 0, meaning we have constant values
 - Simplifies the implementation of kernels
- Each data point is called a *degree of freedom* (DOF)

Order 0

a) $W_0, k = 0$

c) $W_1, k = 0$

Order 1

b) $W_0, k = 1$

d) $W_1, k = 1$

Some images taken from
The LFRic Infrastructure:
Its design and use

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LFRic Fields

- Fields are defined for one of the function spaces and store all DOFs
- Fields are a 1D data structure
 - All columns of a (local) grid are stored as a 1D array
- Size of this data structure depends on element order
 - E.g. W0 with order 0 has 8 points
W0 with order 1 has 27 points etc

a) $W_0, k = 0$

c) $W_1, k = 0$

b) $W_0, k = 1$

d) $W_1, k = 1$

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Continuous / Discontinuous Function Spaces

- Fields can be continuous, or discontinuous
- In LFRic:
 - W3 (red points) discontinuous
 - W0, W1, W2 continuous
 - There are additional discontinuous, special function spaces: `wtheta`, `w2v`, `w2vtrace`, `w2broken`
Please ask a FE expert for more details ☺
- Continuous function spaces have shared points
 - Important to be aware of when parallelising
 - PSyclone thoroughly checks for this

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Getting the Data for a Column – Dofmap

- One column is passed to a kernel by the PSy-layer
- Each field has a 2D-DOF map indicating where each of the DOFs for each column start

	W	S	E	N	B	T
Col 1	1	5	9	13	17	18
Col 2	22	26	30	5	34	35
Col 3	39	43	47	26	51	52

Height ↑

- Then one entry for each level consecutive in memory
- W2 continuous, shared faces!

Col 1	1
Col 2	5
Col 3	9

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(Some) Arguments To Kernels

- Besides the declared fields
 - Number of layers
 - Number of DOFs
 - Number of unique DOFs (all DOFs without double-counting)
 - ATM only used to declare work arrays, since kernels only use standard Fortran arrays
 - Support for kernels that operate on DOFs (instead of columns) is being added.
 - Dofmap for the column
 - I.e. only a 1D array, just the row

Height

	W	S	E	N	B	T
Col 1	1	5	9	13	17	18
Col 2	22	26	30	5	34	35
Col 3	39	43	47	26	51	52

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Typical LFRic Kernel

```

subroutine testkern_w0_code(nlayers, fld1, ndf_w0, &
                           undf_w0, map_w0)
  integer(kind=i_def), intent(in)                :: nlayers
  integer(kind=i_def)                            :: ndf_w0, &
                                                    undf_w0
  real(kind=r_def), dimension(undf_w0), intent(inout) :: fld1
  integer(kind=i_def), dimension(ndf_w0)         :: map_w0
  do k=0, nlayers-1
    do i=1, ndf_w0
      ! Do something with fld1(map_w0(i)+k)
    end do
  end do

```

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Kern Meta Data

- Same concept as GOcean. Example:


```

type, public, extends(kernel_type) :: testkern_w0_kernel_type
  private
    type(arg_type), dimension(1) :: meta_args =
      (/ arg_type(gh_field, gh_real, gh_readwrite, w3), &
      /)
    integer :: operates_on = cell_column
  contains
    procedure, nopass :: code => testkern_w0_code
  end type testkern_w0_kernel_type
public :: testkern_w0_code
      
```
- Note that `nlayers`, `undf_w0`, `map_w0` are not declared

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Kernel Arguments

- First argument: type
`GH_FIELD`, `GH_SCALAR`,
`GH_OPERATOR` for LMA (local matrix assembly),
`GH_COLUMNWISE_OPERATOR` for CMA (column matrix assembly)
- Second argument: data type
`GH_REAL`, `GH_INTEGER`, `GH_LOGICAL`
- Third argument:
`GH_READ`, `GH_WRITE`, `GH_READWRITE` (no shared DOF),
`GH_INC` (shared DOF), `GH_READINC` (READ+INC), `GH_SUM`
- Fourth argument (not for scalars): function space:
`w0`, `w1`, `w2`, `w3`, `wtheta`, `wchi`, ...,
`ANY_SPACE_n`, `ANY_DISCONTINUOUS_SPACE_n`

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More Meta Data

- `operates_on` – which data the kernel expects
 - `cell_column` – 'standard' – a single columns of cells
 - `DOF` – currently built-ins only, ticket in progress to add generic support
 - `domain` – all columns of cells, mostly (only) for interface to UM physics
 - UM physics 'kernel' copy data from LFRic format to UM, call UM, copy results back
 - So, they are not really kernels

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The Real Truth About Kernel Arguments

- There are a lot more
 - 4 pages of implicit arguments added to a kernel
 - Stencil, quadrature, meta-reference-element, meta-mesh, shape, evaluator target
- Specific tool: `psyclone-kern`
 - Takes module file with kernel-meta-data as input
 - Returns the declaration of all arguments for the subroutine
 - (needs an empty subroutine with no arguments)
- That's why I don't start this training with LFRic:
 The complexity of the arguments (ordering ... nlayers at front, others at end), some of which use additional 'meta types', complexity of array access (DOF map), shared elements, basis function evaluation, ...

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LFRic PSy-Layer

```

field1_proxy = field1%get_proxy()
field1_data => field1_proxy%data
map_w0 => field1_proxy%vspace%get_whole_dofmap()
nlayers = field1_proxy%vspace%get_nlayers()
...
DO cell = loop0_start, loop0_stop, 1
    CALL testkern_w0_code(nlayers, field1_data, &
                        ndf_w0, undf_w0, map_w0(:,cell))
END DO
    
```

- proxy – work around for private declaration

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Builtins

- LFRic supports built-ins
- ‘Standard’ / frequently used operations that are inlined. E.g.:
 - setval_c, X_plus_Y, inc_X_plus_Y
 - Approximately 70 builtins, mostly linear algebra.
 - <https://psyclone.readthedocs.io/en/latest/dynamo0p3.html#built-ins>
- PSyclone will create the loops and the code in the PSyLayer
- Same invoke syntax:


```

call invoke( setval_c(f1, asum), &
            inc_a_times_X(asum, f1) )
            
```

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Example PSyLayer of Builtin

```

loop0_start = 1
loop0_stop = field_3_proxy%vspace%get_last_dof_owned()
loop1_start = 1
loop1_stop = field_0_proxy%vspace%get_last_dof_owned()

DO df = loop0_start, loop0_stop, 1
  ! Built-in: setval_c (set a real-valued field to a real scalar value)
  field_3_data(df) = 0.0_r_def
END DO

...

DO df = loop1_start, loop1_stop, 1
  ! Built-in: inc_a_times_X (scale a real-valued field)
  f1_data(df) = bvalue * f1_data(df)
END DO

```

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Builtins Loops

- Built-ins iterate over the DOFs, not columns!
- A DOF is only visited once
 - In a kernel, W0, W1, W2 will be visited up to 8, 4, 2 times
- Makes parallelisation of builtins much easier
 - Esp. when updating elements on W0, W1, W2
- Careful with loop fusion, fields might have same #columns, but not #DOFs
 - Easier with loop over columns / kernels – number of columns is the same (except for multigrid)

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Setting up LFRic

1. Define global mesh (2d grid)
2. Partition information (including stencil info)
3. Extrusion (level information)
4. Define mesh as global-mesh * extrusion → 3d grid
5. Define function space (depend on mesh)
6. Declare fields on function space
7. Call/invoke kernels
 - For hands-on session, we use the unit-testing to create a (3x3) mesh
 - Full setup is a lot more complex
 - Hands-on session documents this in more detail

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Hands-on

- training/tutorial/lfric/4.2
- Follow the README:
 - First finish the kernel
 - Then add OpenMP
 - Note that in LFRic kernels are 'bigger' (loop over column elements, as opposed to a single floating-point number in GOcean), so typically openmp is done per kernel

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14.2 PSyclone's LFRic Domain - Hands-on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/lfric/4.2](https://github.com/PSyclone/tutorial/tree/master/training/lfric/4.2)

In this session you will implement/complete a simple LFRic kernel, and add a script to add OpenMP parallelisation. The example code is the same used in the *PSyclone for LFRic Users* training, but this time the actual code will be explained in more details, and the actual PSyclone transformations will be implemented. The program creates two fields on a 3x3 mesh with 5 layers, mostly by using the testing functionality included in the LFRic infrastructure (the diagrams show only a 2x1x4 mesh). It uses the simplified infrastructure files used in PSyclone testing, and as such can be compiled and run without the need to install LFRic.

We define two fields, one on the W0 space (blue dots) which is initialised with 1, the other will contain the results and it is on the W3 space, and it is initialised with 0.

The kernel `summation_w0_to_w3_kernel` is called, which adds up the 8 neighbouring vertices of field (resulting in 8 on the W3 field). The summation for the top left element is indicated in the image to the right with dashed lines:

14.2.1 Initialising LFRic

The full initialisation of LFRic is reasonable complex, we use a simplified approach here by relying on testing functionality provided by some objects to create our mesh. We start with creating the 2D, 3x3 mesh (which is what the default constructor does for testing):

```
global_mesh = global_mesh_base_type()
```

After that we create a partition, which is a simple 1 process setup. The call

```
extrusion = uniform_extrusion_type(0.0_r_def, &
                                   100.0_r_def, 5)
```

creates level information - in this case we create 5 levels, with an atmosphere bottom of 0, and top of 100. The extrusion is then combined with the 2D global mesh to create our 3x3x5 grid:

```
extrusion_ptr => extrusion
mesh = mesh_type(global_mesh_ptr, partition, extrusion_ptr)
```

Then we declare two vector spaces on our mesh, one on W3 and one on W1:

```
vector_space_0 = function_space_type(mesh, element_order,
                                     W0, ndata_sz)
vector_space_3 = function_space_type(mesh, element_order,
                                     W3, ndata_sz)
```

The input value `element_order` is defined to be 0, meaning our finite elements only store a single value (a constant function).

We then define two fields, one for each of the two vector spaces:

```
call field_0%initialise(vector_space = vector_space_ptr_0,  
                        name="field_3" )  
call field_3%initialise(vector_space = vector_space_ptr_3,  
                        name="field_0" )
```

The field `field_0` is on the vertices of the finite element (W_0 function space, blue in the diagram above). The field `field_3` is on the W_3 function space (red in the diagram).

Then we initialise the fields with 0 and 1 respectively, which is done using a PSyclone builtin for LFRic:

```
call invoke( name = 'Initialise_fields',      &  
            setval_c( field_3, 0.0_r_def ), &  
            setval_c( field_0, 1.0_r_def ) &  
            )
```

We add one `invoke`, and call the `setval_c` (set constant) kernel for the two fields individually. After that, we use `invoke` to call the summation kernel:

```
call invoke( name = 'summation',  
            summation_w0_to_w3_kernel_type(field_3,field_0) )
```

There is no need to use two `invokes`, it was only done to show how PSyclone will create one module with two PSy-layer subroutines.

Todo

First of all, the kernel needs to be completed. All the meta-data, subroutine declaration and even loops are already there, but you still need to add the computation. Once this is done, you can run `make compile` to compile and link your example and execute it. The output should be:

```
Mesh has          5 layers.  
20240917233109.668+1000:INFO : Min/max minmax of field_3 =  
0.800000000E+01  0.800000000E+01
```

Now finish `openmp.py` to add OpenMP parallelisation.

15. LFRic's Redundant Computation and Colouring

This chapter explains the support in PSyclone for redundant computation, an optimisation that reduces halo-exchanges if a value can be computed locally. Then it explains how OpenMP parallelisation is applied in LFRic, even in case of shared values across finite elements - using the colouring transformation.

15.1 LFRic's Redundant Computation and Colouring - Slides

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Common LFRic Code Modifications

- The LFRic build system will apply:
 - A custom script for a file if there is one in optimisations/SITE/PATH_TO_FILE/filename.py
 - If not, it will apply SITE/global.py
- The future FAB build system will support the same
 - Though it is even more flexible ☺
- Most applications (except some really tiny one, e.g. 'skeleton') apply three transformations:
 - Redundant Computations
 - Colouring
 - OpenMP

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Redundant Computations aka Annexed DOFs

- Shared DOFs 'belong' to one of the cells (lowest index number)
- Imagine that the two columns are split across two processes (distributed memory)
- If a shared DOF is updated, by default only the 'owner' will compute it
 - When that data is read, we need a halo exchange

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Annexed DOFs Optimisation

- In order to reduce #halo exchanges, PSyclone can compute 'annexed' DOFs
 - i.e. DOFs that belong to another FE
 - Setting in the config file to enable (I don't know why this way ☹)
- Reduces number of halo exchanges
- But:
 - We need to modify `setval` to initialise these annexed dofs
 - Which is done with the transformation `Dynamo0p3RedundantComputationTrans` in the function `redundant_computation_setval` of `global.py`
 - Why this way? No idea, very inconsistent and dangerous

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OpenMP Parallelisation of Continuous Fields

- OpenMP parallelisation is over columns
 - Except for builtins
- How to parallelise kernels that update shared DOFs?
 - If the two columns shown are updated by different threads, both would update e.g. the shared W0 points ○
 - End up with race condition
- Solution:
 - Avoid working on neighbouring columns in parallel
 - Aka: colouring

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Colouring

- Imagining that the 2D base mesh is coloured, so that no two columns that touch each other (not even diagonal) have the same colour
- Then all columns of the same colour can be executed in parallel
- Replace loop over all columns with two loops:
 - Outer loop over all colours
 - Inner loop over all columns of the given colour
- The inner loop can be parallelised

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Colouring Transformation

- Colouring transformation `Dynamo0p3ColourTrans` in `PSyclone` does this for you. Output (plus OpenMP):

```
DO colour = loop0_start, loop0_stop, 1
  DO cell = loop1_start, last_halo_cell_all_colours(colour,1), 1
    CALL update_w0_with_w0_kernel_code(nlayers, field_3_data, ... )
  END DO
END DO
```

- Outer loop has `loop_type` "colour", and should not be parallelised:

```
for child in schedule.children:
  if isinstance(child, Loop):
    if child.loop_type == "colours":
      otrans.apply(child.loop_body[0])
    else:
      otrans.apply(child)
```

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Hands-on

- Tutorial/training/lfric/4.4
- Try to apply omp directives directly
 - Should all fail since PScyclone detects the race condition
- Apply colouring first
 - Then apply openmp to inner loop

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15.2 LFRic's Colouring - Hands-on

Directory: [PSyclone/tutorial/training/lfric/4.4](#)

In this session you will add openmp parallelisation for an LFRic kernel that updates shared values, which will require colouring.

In this example a kernel adds a field on the W0 space (vertices) to another field on the W0 space, i.e. it is adding the blue dots in the diagram above for two fields. The difference to the kernel used previously is that the vertices (blue dots) are shared between neighbouring columns (indicated by the circled blue dots), which is not the case for a field on the W3 space. Therefore, the loop over all columns cannot be parallelised, since the shared vertices could be read and written by different threads at the same time.

Running PSyclone with the OpenMP transformation script:

```
psyclone -api lfric -s ./omp_transformation.py -dm
        -l output -opsy main_alg_psy.f90
        -oalg main_alg.f90 main_alg.x90
```

(or run `make transform`) will raise an exception:

```
Transformation Error: Error in DynamoOMPParallelLoopTrans
transformation. \
The kernel has an argument with INC access. Colouring is
required.
```

Todo

Finish the `omp_colour_transformation.py` script to first apply colouring where required. Then apply OpenMP to all loops, but in case that a loop is coloured, the OMP directive must be applied to the first child.

The code create should now look like this:

```
DO colour = loop2_start, loop2_stop, 1
  !$omp parallel do default(shared), private(cell),
    schedule(static)
  DO cell = loop3_start, last_edge_cell_all_ &
    colours(colour), 1
    CALL summation_w0_to_w0_code(nlayers_field_3,
      field_3_data, field_0_data, ndf_w0, undf_w0,
      map_w0(:, cmap(colour, cell)))
  END DO
  !$omp end parallel do
END DO
```